

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Investigative research for occurrences of hydrogen, helium, methane and carbon dioxide in West Macedonia: linking geological reservoirs to subsurface gas generation and migration

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Abstract

Background

Climate change, the need for energy optimisation and higher efficiency have led to the adoption of the Paris Agreement as a response to the urge for action. The European Union has translated the aforementioned into an action framework via the Green Deal and the EU taxonomy regulation. These have initiated a series of research actions under the EU Horizon programme. Part of this research is based on carbon dioxide capture and geological storage, such as the Pilot Strategy, and hydrogen storage, such as the HyStorIES, both Horizon 2020 project. A focused hydrogeochemical survey as part of a larger mapping survey was conducted in West Macedonia to identify a potentially suitable location for gas reservoirs, gas sources and gas migration routes based on previous research. Gases investigated were hydrogen, helium, methane and carbon dioxide. The study involved isotopes to identify the source of gases and thus provide clues for generation and migration routes.

Methods

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The investigation presented in this study deployed sequential spring and borehole water sampling for geochemical analysis of trace elements and gas analysis for hydrogen, helium, methane and carbon dioxide to identify and characterise gaseous geological reservoirs. The investigation extended into isotope studies for $d^{13}C_{TDC}$, $d^{13}C_{CH_4}$, dD_{CH_4} , δD_{H_2O} , $\delta^{18}O_{H_2O}$.

Results

The analysis provided evidence for the existence of helium, biogenic methane, carbon dioxide and traces of hydrogen that need to be further investigated for validation and better understanding of the gas generation and migration routes.

Conclusions

The data suggests the existence of helium, methane, carbon dioxide and validated trace concentrations of hydrogen from previous studies in the wider area. Isotopic analysis provides strong evidence for biotic generation of methane, whereas helium comes from a deeper source. This preliminary investigation indicates the existence of multiple gas generation and migration mechanisms and paves the way for further research.

Plain language summary

As our humanity evolves, we realise that our current way of converting energy is not sustainable, it creates geopolitical tensions, competition for resources and results in climate change. The future of the current generation and future ones is at stake. We have already experienced the results of climate change and its direct impacts on the food production chain, as well as water scarcity, manifesting themselves in cost and price increases in developed countries, whereas in underdeveloped and developing countries, the situation is difficult to estimate, but it is even worse. Our research focuses on alternative ways of managing energy and carbon dioxide storage to battle climate change for a just society. In addition, we investigate alternative localised natural sources of energy such as natural hydrogen and methane to support energy independence for prosperous societies.

Keywords

helium, methane, natural hydrogen, geological storage, gas migration, isotope, geological reservoirs

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Introduction

The relatively recent political change on tackling the climate change issue has been expressed with the Paris Agreement¹ on a global scale. The Green Deal² in the European Union has signalled the way forward for the energy transition and decarbonisation of industry. The urgent need to address greenhouse gas emissions from fossil fuel combustion has led to a major transition toward alternative energy sources³. Carbon capture and storage^{4,5} technology has provided an intermediate solution to keep business as usual before more holistic approaches are employed that will allow for a smoother technical and social transition everywhere. Renewable energy, including wind turbines and solar panels, can be part of the solution given that their cost is highly reduced, albeit the issue of the instability they create to the grid they tend to produce during surplus energy not absorbed by demand.

To store the excess energy and stabilise the grid, various feasible solutions have been presented. Some include pumped storage hydropower, compressed air storage, underground carbon dioxide circulation as a medium to harvest thermal energy and convert it again to electricity⁶, compressed air storage and green hydrogen production produced by hydrolysis that can be temporarily stored in lined rock caverns, salt cavities or saline aquifers and depleted hydrocarbons fields⁷. Underground hydrogen storage and geological carbon storage have been developed almost in tandem, and the latter has drawn on substantial technical knowledge from the former. Lately, hydrogen and its potential use as a fuel alternative that can stabilise the grid and decarbonise the industry have received a lot of attention. One of the main issues with green hydrogen is that it is a relatively expensive technology to implement, which has an impact on developing countries that may not be able to adopt the technology, despite recognising its importance. As the scientific society strives to find solutions to advance the democratisation of energy and address climate change, the aforementioned technologies have serendipitously led to discoveries and the conceptualisation of natural hydrogen resources. In a similar fashion, work on Pilot Strategy, an EU Horizon2020-funded project related to Carbon Geological Storage, has stumbled upon what appears to be natural hydrogen and helium gas emission during field geological investigation to identify suitable carbon dioxide reservoir rock storage in West Macedonia, Greece. This is the subject of the present scientific publication, which is elaborated in the subsequent sections and investigates the soundness of the scientific hypothesis of natural hydrogen occurrence in West Macedonia.

Current state of the art of natural hydrogen

The concept of natural hydrogen, although not new, still remains in its infancy with only a handful of researchers together and some pioneer industries actively pursuing the subject to identify large and constant sources that will be able to support a reliable energy transition without leaving anyone behind^{8–12}.

Based on stochastic modelling earth is estimated to be capable of producing some 5.6×10^6 Mt of hydrogen. While most

of it is unrecoverable because its accumulation is too deep, too small in volume, dispersed, or too far away offshore. Still, if a small portion of this, such as 10^5 Mt, can be recovered, it would be able to supply the global needs for 200 years with net-zero carbon emissions¹³. This will provide enough time to achieve nuclear fusion¹⁴ and make the next revolutionary step in human civilisation history based on the Kardashev scale¹⁵.

Promising results for natural hydrogen have already been provided in Mali¹⁶, in Namibia¹⁷, in Colombia¹⁸, in Australia¹⁹, and in the Balkans in Albania and Kosovo²⁰. Daskalopoulou *et al.*, 2018²¹, have also reported traces of natural hydrogen in West Macedonia together with helium and methane. Natural hydrogen mechanisms are still under development, but in general include:

- 1) Contact of water with reducing agents in the mantle^{22–24}.
- 2) Reaction of water with ultrabasic rocks, serpentinization²⁵-type reactions involving the reduction of water by iron-rich minerals have generally been regarded as requiring high temperatures ($>200^\circ\text{C}$)²⁶, although this has been recently challenged with observation at lower temperature conditions ($<200^\circ\text{C}$)^{27,28}.
- 3) Reduction of water by iron-rich minerals in banded iron formations^{29,30} or biotite-rich granites³¹.
- 4) High-thermal maturity organic-rich rocks^{32,33}.
- 5) Decomposition of organic matter²² of NH_3 to N and H_2 at high temperature (up to 600°C).
- 6) Natural electrolysis of water³⁴.
- 7) Natural radiolysis of water^{19,22}.
- 8) Mantle degassing^{22,35}.
- 9) Biological activity²⁵ via microbes in soils and coal beds.
- 10) Cataclasis^{22,23} during earthquakes.

Hydrogen is highly reactive and susceptible to redox conditions, so preservation throughout migration is a risk¹³. In addition, microbial communities are capable of utilising and producing hydrogen that exists in the subsurface³⁶. Thus, understanding the mechanisms of hydrogen generation, residence time in reservoirs, biotic and abiotic loss are essential for guiding its exploration and sustainable production. This is also making sure that resource exploitation approaches of the past, whose activities harmed the environment, its ecosystem services, and human health, will not be repeated. On the same note, to reach the carbon net-zero targets, deploying natural hydrogen in the EU will be based on investment and development of exploration and production strategies¹³ that will satisfy the taxonomy regulation objectives^{37–41}. Exploration itself at this current stage is based on research and development of natural hydrogen conceptual geological models. The latter will allow for global investigation of related geological analogues as a prospective place for exploitation.

Previous research related to West Macedonia and neighbouring areas

The PilotSTRATEGY project, funded by the Horizon2020 programme, investigates geological CO₂ storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe to support the development of large-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS). It is the successor of the StrategyCCUS project, also funded by the Horizon 2020 programme and consequently builds upon the research funding of its predecessor⁵. In Greece, West Macedonia, PilotSTRATEGY focuses on the deep saline aquifers, porous rock formations filled with brine several kilometres below ground, which promise a large capacity for storing CO₂ captured from industrial clusters. The project investigates the geomechanical characteristics and the geological storage capacity of the Mesohellenic Basin⁴². However, during the investigation, an additional research area related to hydrogen occurrences was identified. To better understand this, studies from geologically related areas are examined to provide insight into the mechanisms of hydrogen generation and migration. Where possible, geological analogues will be sought out to draw similarities and conclusions for further work and exploration.

Research conducted by Levy *et al.*, 2023²⁰ has identified hot spots of hydrogen occurrences in Albania and Kosova. The study comprised the collection of water samples from natural springs that were analysed against C and H isotopes of CH₄ and H₂ when that was feasible. Four springs out of 21 sites provided strong evidence for H₂ occurrence. The recent finding in Albania, given the geological proximity and affinity to a certain extent, suggests that similar results may appear in Greece in the Mesohellenic basin.

The Mirdita ophiolite in Albania presents interest and a potential analogue as it is located in the Albanides mountain belt that is a segment of the Dinarides–Albanides–Hellenides orogen. It is bounded on the east by the Pelagonian block and on the west by the Krasta, Cukali, and Kruja zones. The latter is well-known for its geothermal potential due to thrust faults that allow hot fluids percolation. The western massifs of the Mirdita ophiolite are mantle domes of harzburgite (peridotite composed of olivine and orthopyroxene and small amounts of chromium-rich spinel) capped by mylonitic plagioclase-amphibole peridotite of 400 m thickness. Harzburgite peridotite is composed of olivine and orthopyroxene and small quantities of chromium-rich spinel formed in the upper mantle⁴³. The eastern massifs of the Mirdita ophiolite are mainly harzburgite. The northeastern part of the ophiolite complex can reach 14 km in thickness, whereas the west and southeast are estimated to be 2 km thick²⁰. In Kosova, ophiolites are present in most of the country, while of interest to this work are the ophiolites of the West Vardar zone, part of the Dinarides, in the continuity of Mirdita ophiolite. Of similar interest is the central ophiolite of Kosova that has hydrothermally metamorphosed, leading to the economic precipitation of magnesite²⁰.

In Central Greece, Tsikouras *et al.* (2013)⁴⁴ and Etiope *et al.* (2013)⁴⁵ investigated 21 ophiolitic springs in the serpentinised Othrys ophiolite. Four hyperalkaline springs (pH 10.7–11.3)

with calcium-rich (Ca–OH) waters indicated the presence of methane and hydrogen. These springs, one in Archani and three in Ekkara, are located along creeks and tectonically related to faults that are directly linked to the main regional active fault system. An estimation revealed that collectively the springs produce some 100 kg/year of methane⁴⁵. In contrast, methane flux from the soil surrounding the Ekkara well in a 300 m² area gives an estimated methane production of 70 kg per year⁴⁵. The remaining 17 springs, which had pH<8.7 values, did not show detectable CH₄ or H₂.

The Othrys ophiolite complex is located in central Greece, specifically within the Dinaric–Hellenic ophiolite belt and lies uncomfortably into the Pelagonian carbonate platform. It represents an obduction event where an oceanic lithosphere has been thrust onto continental crust. The sampling location area was within the Archani and Ekkara area, at the southwestern part of the Othrys ophiolite, where outcrops of medium- to coarse-grained serpentinised harzburgite with lesser plagioclase-bearing lherzolite are present. These are complemented by dunite forming thin layers, a few cm to a few meters thick, intercalated in the harzburgite. A remnant doleritic sheeted-dyke complex is tectonically overlain by peridotites. Whitish rodingite dykes are found in serpentinised harzburgites very close to the Archani spring²⁸. The peridotites are in tectonic contact with an ophiolitic mélange, which in turn tectonically overlies a Late Cretaceous-Tertiary flysch. An active fault zone, along the Leontari-Anavra line, is found north of Ekkara, at the south border of the Thessaly Plain^{28,44,45}.

The water spring isotope chemical analysis of CH₄ has revealed that the origin of the methane is not biotic. Thus, in hyperalkaline high silica fluids can positively influence the production of H₂ whereas low silica fluids may result in low H₂ production. Othrys springs albeit hydrogen positive, still are releasing low amounts of H₂ compared to other similar places^{28,44,45}. This can be attributed to:

- (i) normal hydrogen generation due to interaction with low-silica fluids alone, followed by consumption through CO₂ hydrogenation and/or loss to the surface as water degasses. Note that H₂ solubility is much less compared to CH₄, by about an order of magnitude.
- (ii) direct methanation processes involving both low- and high-silica fluids^{13,44,45}. High-silica activity promotes the formation of talc or other silica-rich phases, which consumes Mg and reduces the production of brucite (Mg(OH)₂), thereby lowering H₂ generation.
- (iii) Microbial activity that consumes hydrogen.
- (iv) Temperature decrease or modifications in water–rock ratios⁴⁵

Daskalopoulou *et al.*, 2018²¹, in their study, identified in West Macedonia and particularly in Katakali and Mesohori, traces of helium and hydrogen with significant values of methane. Katakali provided 4 ppm He, 11 ppm H₂ and 880.000 ppm CH₄. The Mesohori sample registered 4 ppm He, 1.5 ppm H₂ and

479 ppm CH₄. These values albeit low are indicative and worth investigating to understand the underlying fluid generation and migration.

Derived geological conceptual model to be used as an analogue

Areas with potential for natural hydrogen exploration/exploitation require a source of sufficient hydrogen generation, a mechanism for vertical and lateral fluid migration, porous rock reservoirs for storage, and low permeability rocks (seals) to prevent leakage and allow for economically viable reserves. An additional component that relates to preservation needs to be considered due to hydrogen's high reactivity and microbial consumption. Natural hydrogen is generated in high depths, while it is consumed in shallow ones⁴⁶.

The main takeaway from the previous sections is that the detection of abiogenic methane, brucite and carbonates is a useful indicator for the presence of natural hydrogen^{17,47}. These indicators may be found together or individually in the field with closely related ultrabasic rocks. Helium is also generated by decay of radiogenic nuclides in similar rocks and can be related to natural hydrogen⁴⁶. The presence of talc indicates low chances of hydrogen being freely available. In hyperalkaline systems of Ca-OH, high-silica fluids decrease H₂ production, whereas low-silica fluids enhance H₂ generation. Evidence of low silica activity can be indicated by magnetite abundance and the formation of garnet⁴⁵. Hyperalkaline springs found in ophiolites are related to serpentinization²⁰ via the following general chemical Equation 1:

In terms of the geological setting of interest, ophiolites are thrust and overlain by carbonate rocks, which can provide ample quantities of CO₂, leading to the following very slow reaction (Equation 2) but nonetheless important over geological time:

whereas thrust and other related faults allow for fluid percolation from deep aquifers below or from rainwater above to enable the above reactions to take place. Reaction described in Equation 2 can be catalysed by magnetite (Fe₃O₄), chromite (FeCr₂O₄) and awaruite (Ni₃Fe), at temperatures above 200 °C^{45,48}.

Geological setting for West Macedonia

The Mesohellenic Trough (MHT), or Mesohellenic Basin (MHB), is a late-orogenic, molassic-type basin that developed from the Middle Eocene to Middle Miocene in northwestern Greece and southern Albania⁴⁹. It is presented as a favourable area with a potential for hydrogen accumulations associated with the long-distance lateral flow migration that commonly occurs in sedimentary basins. Long-distance lateral migration is defined as migration across map distances of up to 250 km⁴⁶. Figure 1 depicts the location of the Mesohellenic Trough (cyan-dashed lines) and of the Florina, Ptolemais-Amyntaio, Kozani-Servia, Sarandaporos Basins (red-dashed lines) across northern Greece. Major mountains and lakes are highlighted. The inset map depicts the study area (red rectangle) with respect to the geotectonic zones and the major tectonic features of the Hellenic Orogen and the Aegean domain⁵⁰.

The MHT extends over 200 km in a NNW-SSE direction and is 20 to 40 km wide, lying along the suture between the

Figure 1. Satellite imagery showing the location of the Mesohellenic Trough, SAVA = South Aegean Volcanic Arc, NAFZ = North Anatolian Fault Zone, modified after Stergiou *et al.*, 2025⁵⁰ and provided under licence: CC-BY 4.0.

Apulian plate and the Pelagonian nappe pile, thus marking the boundary between the Internal and External Hellenides⁵¹⁻⁵³. The basin formed atop westward-emplaced Tethyan ophiolites following their final emplacement between Middle and Late Eocene during the Alpine orogeny, with subsidence driven by crustal loading and flexure^{49,54}. The southern part of the basin is structurally divided by the Theopetra-Theotokos Structure, a horst or faulted anticline, which separates the basin into western and eastern sub-basins. These are represented by the Pentalofon and Tsotyli–Ondria formations, respectively.

The stratigraphy of the MHT is subdivided into seven major lithostratigraphic units⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸. These include: 1) the Middle-Upper Eocene Krania Formation (Fm) incorporating conglomerates and olistoliths (lower sequence) and turbiditic beds (upper sequence) with a thickness of 1500 m, 2) the Oligocene Eptachorion Fm with silty marls and very-fine sandstone beds overlying thick conglomerates (~1000 m in thickness), 3) the Upper Oligocene-Lower Miocene Taliaros/Tsarnos Fm and the equivalent Pentalofos Fm, showing sequences from sandstones to conglomerates (~2500 m in thickness), 4) the Lower to Middle Miocene Tsotyli Fm with marl-sandstone alternations in the north and conglomerates in the south (~600 m in thickness), and 5) the Ondria Fm and the equivalent Orlias Fm (Lower to Middle Miocene) comprising fossiliferous limestones, marls, and sandstones (≥350 m in thickness). These MHT

thick sedimentary strata, as a geological reservoir, offer the benefit of (1) sufficient burial to compact rocks to low porosity and (2) a higher likelihood of one or more potential sealing formations throughout the stratigraphic sequence⁴⁶. Tyrologou *et al.* 2023 have confirmed with field surveys and laboratory investigation the existence of favourable rock sealing conditions related to the Pentalofos, Eptachori and Tsotyli sedimentary formations⁴² due to their low porosity and permeability values.

Major tectonic unconformities define the bases of the Krania, Eptachorion, and Tsotyli Formations. Lithologies within these formations include conglomerates of fan-delta and alluvial fan origin, turbiditic sandstones and shales, as well as deltaic, floodplain, and shelf sandstones and siltstones⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷. These sediments show a general coarsening trend from north to south and were deposited during a progressive shallowing of the basin, with a maximum sedimentary thickness reaching 4.5 km near Grevena^{51,59}. These sedimentary facies hold potential as porous media capable of economically accumulating hydrogen while being protected from overlain low permeability rocks described previously. Upper Miocene unconformably overlies the molassic sequence to Quaternary deposits.

The MHT depicted in Figure 2 is bounded to the west by the Pindos mountain range, comprising Triassic to Jurassic ophiolites, mélangé units, Cretaceous limestones, and Maastrichtian

Figure 2. Modified Geological map and isodepths of the basement rocks of the Mesohellenic Basin⁴², licence: CC-BY 4.0.

to Palaeocene flysch deposits⁴⁹. The eastern boundary is defined by the Pelagonian nappe rocks exposed at the Vernon and Askion mountains. They include Precambrian to Palaeozoic metamorphic gneiss and schist, Permo-Triassic rift-related volcanosedimentary successions, and Cretaceous carbonates. Thrusted ophiolitic units are also found, with the Vourinos ophiolitic complex being the most profound one⁶⁰. The MHT has asymmetrical synclinal geometry, with sharp eastward dips at the western boundary and gradual westward dips towards the eastern margin. This asymmetry is ascribed to a combination of depositional tilting and post-depositional tectonic deformation⁵³. The Theopetra-Theotokos Structure in the southern portion of the basin exposes the basement ophiolitic and carbonate units and runs almost parallel to the main basin axis^{53,58}. A complex tectonic development influenced by both brittle and semi-ductile deformation occurred in the basin. The final emplacement of the Pindos ophiolites was associated with strike-slip faulting and NE-verging thrusting during the first tectonic phase (T1, Middle to Late Eocene), which was characterised by a transpressional regime with NE-SW maximum compressive stress. Along NW-SE to NNW-SSE faults, dextral strike-slip tectonics dominated the subsequent phase (T2, Early to Late Oligocene), allowing for lateral basin displacements and subsidence (Figure 3)⁶¹. A shift to extensional tectonics is reflected in later periods (T3 to T5, Miocene to Quaternary), when shifting fault patterns govern sedimentation and depocenter migration. Recent seismicity (e.g. the 1995 Grevena-Kozani earthquake sequence^{62,63}; in the Grevena-Kozani region supports the ongoing N-S extension, which suggests ongoing reactivation of inherited structures within the MHT.

The Jurassic oceanic lithosphere was obducted during the closing of the Mesozoic Tethys Ocean, forming the Vourinos and Pindos ophiolites that are exposed along the edges of the MHT^{52,64}. The Vourinos ophiolite is a well-preserved Penrose-type section made up of pillow lavas, sheeted dikes, a thick ultramafic-mafic cumulate sequence, and mantle peridotites. Hydrothermal activity during seafloor spreading is indicated by features including epidotized dikes, sulfide mineralisation, and jaspers⁶⁵. In contrast, the Pindos ophiolite to the west is made up of a number of petrologically overlapping, tectonically

imbricated nappes that have a total reconstructed thickness reaching 4 km. The upper plutonic suite, which includes dunite, troctolite, and gabbro, and the lower suite, which includes dunite, lherzolite, wehrlite, and pyroxenite, make up its cumulate section, which is less than one kilometre thick and extends from a transitional Moho to the base of the sheeted dike complex⁶⁰. Large sheeted dikes and pillow lavas that have been preserved in tectonic windows and nappe sequences sit on top of this structure. Despite differences in structure and thickness, both ophiolites are classified as supra-subduction zone ophiolites with island arc tholeiitic and boninitic affinities⁶⁰. A continuous magnetic anomaly beneath the Mesohellenic Trough suggests a common ophiolitic root, supporting a shared tectonic origin^{51,65}.

Ophiolites are abundant in the area, offering promising potential as a source rock for natural hydrogen through serpentinization. The underlying Triassic and Jurassic limestones can contribute significant quantities of CO₂, mobilised by migratory fluids that percolate vertically and laterally through the rock mass as a result of the prevailing tectonic setting and associated strain.

The Florina Basin is part of a large NW-SE trending graben system in NW Macedonia, Greece, that formed during the Lower Miocene following the Alpine Orogeny. This graben system (~150 km in length) contains the Florina, Ptolemaida-Amynteo, Kozani-Servia, and Sarandaporo Basins⁶⁶. The basins were initially formed under a NE-SW extensional regime during the Late Miocene, which was succeeded by an Early Pleistocene NW-SE extension. This resulted in the fragmentation of the originally continuous Florina-Ptolemaida-Servia Basin into three sub-basins. Depicted in the synthesised related stratigraphic column in Figure 4, the basement rocks of the basin system include mainly Triassic to Jurassic crystalline limestones, marbles and dolomites, as well as Palaeozoic to Mesozoic schists, phyllites, gneisses, and granites of the Pelagonian Zone⁶⁶. Locally, ophiolitic rocks with serpentinites and serpentinized peridotites occur⁶². As previously discussed, ophiolites present the potential to generate natural hydrogen and can be considered as source rock within the Florina Basin.

Figure 3. Modified geological cross-section of Mesohellenic Basin⁴², licence: CC-BY 4.0.

Figure 4. Synthesized stratigraphic column of the Sarantaporos, Ptolemaida-Amynteo-Florina basins, licence: CC-BY 4.0.

Between Late Miocene and Early Pliocene, these basins began to fill with continental, fluvial, lacustrine, and marshy deposits. At the base lies the Base Formation, composed of red to reddish-brown breccias, conglomerates, sands, clays, and mud, varying in thickness and reflecting proximal alluvial-fan and talus origins. The overlying Clastic Formation includes green to green-grey fluvial sands, clays, hard sandstones, and conglomerates, representing a mature fluvial system. Above, the Lignite Formation is characterised by green-grey sands, clays, silts, plant remains, xylite, and beds of xylitic lignite, and hosts the most important lignite seams of the basin system (e.g. Florina, Komnina⁶⁶). The higher Silt Formation follows, dominated

by silts with interbedded sands, clays, and calcareous silts containing organic remains and vivianite. In areas like eastern Florina, a Sand-clay Formation with green sands and clays replaces the fine lacustrine silts⁶⁶. The Late Neogene Series Formation consists of light grey to grey-green marls, clays, sands, marly limestones, and earthy lignites, containing rich fossil assemblages and significant lignite seams (e.g., Ptolemaida-Amynteo). During the Early–Middle Pleistocene, the Proastion Formation was deposited, comprising fluvial-torrential conglomerates with cross-bedding and minor lignite beds. Sedimentation continued with the development of the Perdika Formation, containing sands, clays, marls, and thin, non-economic lignite beds⁶⁶. Finally, a Middle Pleistocene Terrestrial Formation marks the latest phase, with conglomerates, red loam, clays, and sands, especially thick in Sarandaporo and parts of Florina basins.

Particularly, in the Florina Basin, these deposits also include lignite-bearing formations rich in xylitic-type lignite, especially along its eastern margins, which can generate natural hydrogen^{22,67}. During the Late Pliocene, a widespread lacustrine-marshland system was developed and associated sediments were deposited. Marshy and riverine sediments and lignite were deposited during the Lower Pleistocene, followed by fluvial-terrestrial deposition during the Middle Pleistocene. Peat deposition in the Vegoritida and Zazari lakes is indicative of Holocene sedimentation⁶⁶.

The sedimentary fill of the Florina Basin reaches a total thickness of about 560 m, which is comparable to the 600 m found in the Ptolemais Basin. This suggests that the two sub-basins had a similar geological history up until the early Pleistocene. The basement rocks of the Florina Basin comprise Palaeozoic gneiss, schist and Middle Triassic to Lower Jurassic crystalline limestone, marble and dolomite, which are overlaid by forty-one distinct sedimentary cycles described in three separate formations⁶⁸.

The Base Formation (~251–548 m) consists mainly of alternating sand, clay, and conglomerate beds, interpreted as stacked alluvial fan sequences that grade upward into fluvial deposits. A change from active tectonism and a high sediment supply to a quieter regime with less accommodation space is indicated by this vertical transition. CO₂ accumulations have been found in the fine sand layers of these river deposits, suggesting that they could serve as carbon storage or natural gas reservoir units⁶⁹. The overlying Vevi Formation (~25.1–124 m) records a lacustrine depositional system characterised by 21 distinct sedimentary cycles, where marl, clay and sand dominate. Several sedimentary cycles are capped by lignite seams with a cumulative thickness of up to 6.6 m. Similar deposits are found in the neighbouring Ptolemais Basin, corresponding to Lower Pliocene⁶⁶.

The Lophon Formation (0–124 m) is the uppermost unit and represents a return to fluvial-lacustrine sedimentation during the Early Pleistocene⁶⁶. Lithology is composed of sand, clay, and silt found as beds and marly limestone as lenses.

Cross-bedded conglomerates and sands appear in the upper parts of the stratigraphy. Lophon Formation is distinguished by coarser fluvial interbeds interspersed with fine-grained lacustrine clays and silts⁶⁶. This change indicates a decrease in accommodation space brought on by either increased sediment influx or decreased subsidence, which is probably related to regional elevation and the Quaternary fragmentation of the Florina-Ptolemais-Servia Basins system (Steenbrink *et al.* 2006).

The sedimentary architecture of the Florina Basin supports a viable option for natural hydrogen storage⁷⁰. The river sand deposits of the Base Formation have been shown to naturally accumulate CO₂, providing a useful analogy for subsurface storage behaviour. With alternating permeable sands and impermeable layers like clays and lignites, the lithological variability of the basin offers efficient natural trapping mechanisms that hold natural CO₂ and may also be able to hold natural hydrogen accumulation. Hydrogeochemical analyses show that groundwater quality in regions impacted by natural CO₂ seepage has not significantly declined⁷⁰ indicating the existence of low permeable rocks in the vicinity exhibiting good seal capabilities.

The CO₂ emissions at Florina are ascribed to the regional Quaternary volcanism, and are primarily of crustal origin, including also a restricted mantle input, while NE-SW trending faults serve as fluid migration conduits^{71,72}. Between 2012 and 2014, the Florina region experienced a significant rise in micro-seismicity, with over 2000 events documented and an Mw 4.1 main shock in February 2013. With certain episodes displaying migration patterns suggestive of pore-fluid pressure diffusion, seismicity seemed to be episodic and clustered. Deep CO₂ fluids may play a part in fault zone reactivation, as evidenced by shear-wave splitting investigations that showed anisotropy compatible with the local stress field and fault orientations⁷³⁻⁷⁵.

Localised geological investigation deploying hydrogeology and geochemistry

Previous field investigations conducted as part of the Pilot Strategy Project on CO₂ storage led to the discovery of good low porosity low permeability seal rocks, but did not yield concrete evidence of an adequate reservoir rock⁴². To address this gap, water sampling campaigns targeting zones with elevated gas content were carried out as a proxy to help identify rock formations with potential reservoir properties. While the formations sampled are themselves unsuitable for storage due to leakage, they serve as valuable geological analogues. Identifying these leaky formations will facilitate the recognition of similar, properly bounded rock units in the field that possess the capacity to store CO₂ securely without leakage risk. Collecting data from a) previous research conducted by Daskalopoulou *et al.*, 2018²¹ b) observations investigation in the field using anecdotal data, from publicly available media and c) public indications of water springs with the elevated gas yield, the authors considered the local geology and concluded that the springs presented in Table 1 are promising places for an initial investigation.

The local geology of each water spring and sampling area is summarised based on published geological maps and field observations. Water springs at Katakali and Kivotos emerge through formations of the Mesohellenic Trough, while spring emanations at Tropeouhos, Ammohori, Itea, Marina, Mesohori, Mesocampos and Neos Kafkasos are found at the Florina Basin (Figure 5).

At Katakali, the near surface layers include Pliocene to Lower Pleistocene marls, sandstones, sandy marls, clays, and conglomerates of the Karperon Basin⁷⁶. A small lignite layer within the marls near the Sioutsas river indicates local marsh conditions, while fossil evidence (Planorbis, Neritina, and Radix ovate) suggests freshwater environments. Near basin margins, these

Table 1. Locations of water springs observed and suspected with a high possibility of gas content.

Name	N (WGS84)	E (WGS84)	X (Greek Grid, EGSA 87, m)	Y (Greek Grid, EGSA 87, m)	Z (m)
Katakali	39° 55' 31,15"	21° 40' 37,5"	301337	4421760	404
Kivotos	40° 14' 35,55"	21° 25' 34,62"	280926	4457643	547
Tropeouhos	40° 44' 25,45"	21° 26' 23,87"	283693	4512806	695
Ammohori_1	40° 46' 39,93"	21° 28' 50,51"	287251	4516854	633
Ammohori_2	40° 46' 54,80"	21° 28' 57,69"	287433	4517308	631
Itea	40° 50' 1,64"	21° 30' 59,80"	290459	4522988	613
Marina	40° 51' 44,29"	21° 29' 34,15"	288543	4526211	595
Mesohori	40° 53' 12,92"	21° 29' 16,50"	288208	4528956	589
Mesocampos	40° 53' 39,57"	21° 30' 41,36"	290218	4529721	598
Neos Kafkasos	40° 54' 14,50"	21° 29' 37,49"	288754	4530841	585

Figure 5. Map with the sample location in EGSA 87 grid system, scale 1:800.000, licence: CC-BY 4.0.

sediments transition into unbedded fluvial-torrential deposits. The lower stratigraphy includes:

- 1) the Miocene (Upper Aquitanian to Tortonian) Tsotyli Fm of the MHT (<2200 m in thickness). It is composed of ophiolitic conglomerates at the base, gradually transitioning into sandstones, marls, and sandy marls. The fossil content in the transition beds includes bryozoans (*Retepora gigantea*), corals (*Siderastrea crenulata*, *Ceratotrochus duodecim costatus*), gastropods (*Haustator magnasporulus*, *Turritella* sp., *Gypraea* sp.), and bivalves (*Chlamys multistriata*, *Panopea intermedia*), indicating a marine depositional environment, and
- 2) the Middle to Upper Oligocene Eptachori Fm of the MHT, consisting of ophiolitic conglomerates with lateritic lenses at the base and interbedded sandstones and marls above. This formation lies unconformably over the metamorphic basement and contains a rich microfaunal assemblage (*Millioliidae*, *Textulariidae*, *Cibicides* sp., *Almaena* sp.), pointing to a shallow marine setting during its deposition⁷⁶.

The stratigraphy at Kivotos sampling site comprises Quaternary alluvial sediments, such as loose sands and clays, which are underlain by Pliocene to Pleistocene fluvial and lacustrine deposits forming terrace sequences composed of loose conglomerates, blue to greenish clays, sands, and friable sandstones⁷⁷. The upper parts of this unit are characterised by red clays and conglomerates, suggesting alternating oxidising and reducing conditions in a dynamic depositional setting. Lower the Early Miocene (Aquitanian to Burdigalian) Tsotyli Fm of the MHT

is found (<500 m in thickness), composed of conglomerates, and intercalated sandstones and clastic limestones, that exhibit rapid lateral facies changes and thinning. The fossil content (lamellibranchs, gastropods, algae and *Miogyopsina*) suggests a shallow marine and marginal marine environment⁷⁷. The lowermost unit in the area consists of brecciated Middle to Upper Cretaceous limestones with rudists and marly limestones, representing the tectonically deformed remnants of an older carbonate platform that forms the geological basement of the sequence.

The stratigraphy at Tropeouhos, Ammohori, Itea, Marina, Mesohori, Mesocampos and Neos Kafkasos comprises Neogene sands, clays, and conglomerates that grade downward into massive, whitish-brown to whitish-yellow fossiliferous marly limestones, marls, and clays (<100 metres in thickness)^{68,78}. The presence of thin lignite and xylite layers in the deeper parts indicates episodes of organic-rich deposition in marshy, low-energy environments. Fossil assemblages (*Neritina*, *Theodoxus macedonicus*) support a lacustrine to limnotelmatic depositional setting. Beneath these Neogene sediments lies the Pelagonian metamorphic basement of Palaeozoic age, composed predominantly of orthogneiss and paragneiss with intercalations of schists in the form of layers and lenses, and minor occurrences of amphibolites^{68,78}.

Additionally, at Itea and Mesohori, the local stratigraphy includes Pleistocene conglomerates, sandstones, sands, and red clays, indicating deposition in fluvial to alluvial environments under oxidising conditions (<200 metres in thickness)⁶⁸. These sediments represent a transitional phase between older Neogene

units and more recent Quaternary deposits, reflecting intense weathering, erosion, sediment transport, and soil formation under subaerial conditions during the Pleistocene.

Materials and methods

Water samples for gas measurements were collected in accordance with the UK Environment Agency Methods for sampling and analysing methane in groundwater: a review of current research and practice⁷⁹, as well as Capasso and Inguaggiato, 1998³⁶ and Inguaggiato and Rizzo, 2004⁸⁰. The sample collection method deployed is described below.

The sampling bottles were 100/125/250 ml vials crimped using a Teflon septum (Figure 6). Vial size was determined by the target analysis: 100 ml for carbon isotopes, ≥ 125 ml for noble gas isotopes. The future user/adopter is advised to pay particular attention to shipping and preservation of samples, as, despite the best efforts of the authors, the first two rounds of samples could not be measured reliably for gases in the laboratory due to the hot conditions of South Europe during spring and summer.

As prerequisite actions, before filling the vials with water sample, the vials were fully filled and rinsed with the same water to be sampled from the spring samples 2 or 3 times to reduce contamination.

Prior to the sampling, the spring water was measured against dissolved O_2 (mg/L), Conductivity ($\mu S/cm$), Temp ($^{\circ}C$) and pH. The values of the latter were recorded in field books or digital devices. Physico-chemical conditions of the groundwater (pH, temperature, salinity) can contribute to CO_2 dissolution or release. Differences in He and CO_2 solubility and reactivity can determine the recorded variations in the He/ CO_2 ratio³⁶. The collection should come in doubles. In other words, two (2 nr) bottles of 100 ml, or 125 ml should be collected per location or sampling area. The first bottle is used for carbon, oxygen, hydrogen and helium isotopes, whereas the other bottle is used for gas chromatography (GC). Again, the exact size of the vials is dictated by the analysis to be performed. A balance between cost and volume collected should be established. Prior conduct with the laboratory to perform the analysis is highly recommended.

In bodies of water such as lakes, pools, seawater, or drainage galleries, as well as any location facilitating direct sample

collection beneath the water's surface, it is imperative to submerge and crimp the bottles. This entails placing the bottles underwater, allowing them to fill completely while ensuring that the caps remain submerged at all times to prevent any contact with the atmosphere to avoid any air contamination during the sampling phase. In addition, when the bottle is underwater, it is easier to tightly apply the rubber closure and the aluminium cap, and ensure that no atmospheric air is still trapped in the collected sample. A standard stainless-steel after-market crimper able to cap 8–32 mm aluminium plastic/full aluminium and stainless steel/tight caps was used for sealing the sampling bottles.

Both the rubber closure and aluminium cap (Figure 6) were applied and the vials were moved sideways to check if any air bubbles were visible to the naked eye. Crimping the bottle underwater might be a difficult task as the aluminium cap tends to float towards the surface.

In any sampling action, it was ensured that the bottom of the bottle and the mouth of the crimper were levelled before applying force to the crimper's tongues (Figure 7). Otherwise, the aluminium cap will not be sealed perfectly. The sampling staff is advised to check the manual of the crimper and do considerable practice in sealing bottles before actually undertaking the sampling process. When bottles are sealed, it is advisable to check them again for bubbles under daylight and apply sealing tape around the neck of the bottle, covering also only the sides of the aluminium caps (Figure 7).

For water sampled from taps, a tube of suitable diameter, crafted from either silicone or Teflon, is required. This tube was inserted into the bottles until reaching the bottom, enabling the water to fill the container from bottom to top. Subsequently, the tube is slowly removed, ensuring the vial is entirely filled up to the upper portion of the bottle neck. Extreme care was taken to eliminate any air bubbles during this process, followed by sealing the vial securely to prevent air contamination.

It is recommended that the final procedure be conducted within a cylinder containing an identical sample of water extracted from the tap. This approach ensures the vial is fully submerged upon reaching its capacity, facilitating underwater sealing and crimping with water acting as a barrier to prevent air entrapment.

Figure 6. The 100ml crimp-top glass vial, the 20mm rubber closure (lower left) and aluminium cap (a) and the standard stainless-steel crimper (b), licence: CC-BY 4.0.

Figure 7. Ensuring that the bottom of the bottle and the mouth of the crimper are levelled before applying force to the crimper's tongues (a). Practice a lot after reading the crimper's manual and before commencing the sampling process (b), licence: CC-BY 4.0.

For inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis, employing plastic sterilised (Falcon) 50ml sampler filters (Figure 8), which have been appropriately acidified beforehand, is deemed sufficient.

After the sampling took place, a visual observation of the existence or nonexistence of bubbles was noted. Samples were appropriately numbered on a pre-agreed sampling system and metadata such as location name, coordinates, time and data of sampling, related geological formation and any other observed data were properly recorded. Recording of sample numbers in each sample bottle is vital to minimise analytical problems during the laboratory investigation. All data collected, recorded and subsequently uploaded in SESAR, the System for Earth and Extraterrestrial Sample Registration. Each sample was allocated an International Geo Sample Number (IGSN) to ensure that they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR)⁸¹. The IGSN persistent identifier can link each sample with any analyses performed in any laboratory. Published data can be accessed via hyperlinked journals online. All data can be located via online geological data services or the Zenodo platform.

Four sampling campaigns were distributed across different seasons, with collections in summer 15–19 July 2023, spring 21 – 22 April 2024, late spring/early summer 5–6 June 2024, and late autumn/early winter 29 November–3 December 2024, enabling the assessment of potential seasonal effects such as temperature changes, precipitation patterns, organic matter input, and hydrological dynamics. In each case, the samples were shipped to an external accredited laboratory and specifically to the Laboratory for Stable Isotopes, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia Sezione di Palermo in Italy for geochemical laboratory analysis that followed the below provided protocol.

Samples were analysed for He, H₂, O₂, N₂, CH₄ and CO₂ by gas chromatography (Perkin Elmer Clarus500 equipped with a double Carboxen 1000 column system, TCD-FID detectors) using Ar as the gas carrier. Ar was analysed with a Perkin Elmer

Figure 8. Plastic (Falcon) 50 ml sample filters, license: CC-BY 4.0.

XL gas chromatograph with MSieve 5A column, TCD detector having He as carrier. Analytical uncertainties are $\pm 5\%$. Hydrocarbon analyses were performed with a Shimadzu 14a gas chromatograph equipped with a Flame Ionization Detector (FID) using He as the carrier gas. The analytical error is $\leq 5\%$.

Isotope determinations of $\delta^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ and δD in water samples were performed using the equilibration technique for oxygen and water reduction (hydrogen production using granular Zn) for hydrogen. Measurements were carried out using a FinniganDelta Plus mass spectrometer (Hydrogen) and an automatic preparation system coupled with an AP 2003 IRMS (Oxygen). Analytical precision for each measurement is better than 0.2‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and 1‰ for δD .

Carbon isotope composition of CO₂ was determined by using a Thermo Delta Plus XP, coupled with a Thermo TRACE Gas Chromatograph (GC) and a Thermo GC/C III interface. The TRACE GC is equipped with a Poraplot Q (25 m \times 0.32 mm) column and uses Helium (5.6) as carrier gas at a constant flow of 0.9 cm³ min⁻¹.

Undesired gas species, such as N₂, O₂, and CH₄, are vented to the atmosphere using back-flush of He and a Sige valve. The ¹³C/¹²C ratios are reported as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CO}_2}$ values relative to the V-PDB standard (Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite)⁸². Carbon isotope ratios were determined by comparing three in-house standards ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ranging from $+0.3 \pm 0.1\%$ to $-28.5 \pm 0.3\%$ vs V-PDB calibrated using a CO₂ standard (RM8564⁸³) with known isotopic composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -10.45 \pm 0.04\%$ vs V-PDB) and two international standards (NBS 18 and NBS 19⁸²). External precision, computed as 1 σ (standard deviation) on ten measurements of the same sample, is 0.1‰. The RM8564, NBS 18 and NBS 19 standards can be obtained from the Terrestrial Environment Radiochemistry Laboratory of the International Atomic Energy Agency (<https://analytical-reference-materials.iaea.org/catalogs>, web page accessed on 21/08/2025)

Carbon and Hydrogen isotopes of CH₄, both in free gases and in dissolved gases, were measured using a Thermo TRACE GC interfaced to a Delta Plus XP gas source mass spectrometer and equipped with a Thermo GC/C III (for Carbon) and with GC/TC peripherals (for Hydrogen). The gas chromatograph was equipped with an Rt-Q Plot column (Restek 30 m \times 0.32 mm i.d.) and the oven was held at a constant temperature (50 °C for carbon and 40 °C for Hydrogen). The flow rate of carrier gas (He 5.6 grade) was held at a constant flux of 0.8 cm³ min⁻¹. A split/splitless injector with a split ratio from 10:1 to 80:1 was used for sample introduction, except for diluted samples (CH₄ concentration lower than 10 mmol/mol) when direct on-column injection was performed.

The inlet system consists of a stainless steel loop with a known volume (50 μl), connected to a two-position six-port Valco® valve. Before the introduction of the sample, a vacuum of 10⁻² mbar measured with an EBRO pressure gauge is ensured by a rotary vane pump. Once CH₄ was separated from the gas mixture, it was quantitatively converted to CO₂ by passing

through a combustion oven ($T = 940\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ ratios analysis or to H_2 by passing it through a reactor set at a temperature of $1440\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for $^2\text{H}/^1\text{H}$ ratios analysis. Each sample analysis took about 500 s.

The $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ ratios are reported as $\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CH}_4$ values for the V-P standard and $^2\text{H}/^1\text{H}$ ratios are reported here as $\delta^2\text{H}-\text{CH}_4$ values with respect to the V-SMOW standard. Carbon isotope ratios were determined by comparing an in-house standard ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -49.5 \pm 0.2\text{‰}$) calibrated using four CH_4 standards (Isometric Instruments) with known isotopic composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ranging from $-23.9 \pm 0.3\text{‰}$ to $-66.5 \pm 0.3\text{‰}$ vs V-PDB).

Hydrogen isotope ratios were determined by comparing an in-house standard ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -200 \pm 2.0\text{‰}$) with a CH_4 standard with known isotopic composition ($\delta^2\text{H} = -186.1 \pm 3.0\text{‰}$ vs V-SMOW). External reproducibility, estimated as 1σ (standard deviation) on ten measurements of the same sample, is 0.2‰ and 2.0‰ for carbon and hydrogen isotopes, respectively.

In CO_2 -dominated gases having CH_4 concentrations lower than $1000\text{ }\mu\text{mol/mol}$, the analyses of the isotope ratios of methane were carried out in the headspace gas samples collected using pre-evacuated 60 mL glass flasks filled with 20 mL of a 4 N NaOH solution.

The abundance and isotope composition of He, and the $^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$ ratios, were determined by separately admitting He and Ne into a split flight tube mass spectrometer (Helix SFT). Helium isotope compositions are given as R/RA, where R is the ($^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$) ratio of the sample and RA is the atmospheric ($^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$) ratio ($\text{RA} = 1.386 \times 10^{-6}$). The analytical errors were generally $< 1\%$.

Location names, sampling date and coordinates of all new sampling sites together with raw chemical results can be

found as supplementary material at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16914636>⁸⁴.

Results

Below are presented the results from all four sampling campaigns, starting with the isotope data analysis (Table 2–Table 5). As the samples are from groundwater, the Global Meteoric Water line was deployed to analyse the data rather than the Local Meteoric Water line, which relies on precipitation samples only⁸⁵ (Figure 9).

In the first sample campaign (Table 2, Summer 2023), most samples plot in close proximity to the Global Meteoric Water Line^{86,87}, indicating a meteoric origin with little evaporation enrichment⁸⁸ (Figure 9). Katakali and Tropeouhos in the first round (Table 2) are the most depleted in both isotopes, indicating a colder recharge. Mesocampos and Kivotos are relatively enriched, possibly indicating partial evaporation⁸⁷. Since the elevations of all sampling locations are relatively similar, altitude differences are unlikely to be the primary factor driving the observed isotopic variability. This original investigation did not provide any distinct chemical signature; however, during the Katakali sample collections (#10), there were clear observations of gas bubbles in the water sample. This is due to pressure decreases, causing these dissolved gases to come out of solution and form bubbles.

The second round of data (Table 3) indicated that Tropeouhos, Mesocampos and Neos Kafkasos had a shift towards depletion of isotopes, which indicates hydrologic change. This can be explained by seasonal input⁸⁹. The first batch was collected in Summer (June 2023) during a low rainfall season, whereas the second batch was collected in Spring (April 2024) during a high rainfall season. This is consistent with a well-mixed aquifer or steady-state recharge conditions typical of early spring. This sample location above the GMWL

Table 2. Water samples collected between 15-19/07/2023, laboratory data analysis provided at 06/09/2023, first sample campaign, rounded to two significant figures.

N°	Spring location name	$\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	Dissolved O_2 (mg L^{-1})	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	Temp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	pH
1	Tropeouhos	-72	-10.0	7.9	-	17.5	6.04
2	Mesocampos	-50	-7.4	0.19	1686	16	6.06
3	Neos Kafkasos	-59	-8.5	0.76	575	14.1	6.08
4	Ammohori 1	-64	-9.0	8.3	920	17.5	6.07
5	Itea	-66	-9.6	2.73	1017	16.5	6.03
6	Mesohori	-62	-9.1	1.09	478	14	6.03
7	Ammohori 2	-70	-9.9	7.1	319	20.5	6.01
8	Marina	-68	-9.6	6.3	338	25.6	6.04
9	Kivotos	-57	-8.2	0.24	850	15.3	5.4
10	Katakali	-74	-10.5	0.25	1447	18	6.0

Table 3. Water samples collected between 21-22/04/2023, laboratory data analysis provided at 15/05/2024, second sample campaign.

N°	Spring location name	δD_{H_2O}	$\delta^{18}O_{H_2O}$	Dissolved O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	Conductivity ($\mu S\ cm^{-1}$)	Temp (°C)	pH
1	Tropeouhos	-75.0	-11.9	8.85	1803	14.4	7.5
2	Mesocampos	-59.0	-10.1	2.59	1984	13.5	5.67
3	Neos Kafkasos	-64.0	-11.0	1.60	468	14.5	5.42
4	Ammohori 1	-66.0	-10.7	7.06	971	12	6.49
5	Itea	-62.0	-10.0	2.91	972	13	5.61
6	Mesohori	-66.0	-10.8	2.50	450	13	6.5
7	Ammohori 2	-69.0	-11.2	7.78	318	14.8	5.7
8	Marina	-67.0	-11.2	8.15	347	14.1	6.29
9	Kivotos	-61.0	-10.3	1.75	803	14.9	7.25
10	Katakali	-76.0	-12.0	1.40	1440	16.1	7.5

Table 4. Water samples collected between 05-06/06/2024, laboratory data analysis provided at 24/07/2024, third round campaign.

N°	Spring location name	δD_{H_2O}	$\delta^{18}O_{H_2O}$	Dissolved O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	Conductivity ($\mu S\ cm^{-1}$)	Temp (°C)	pH
1	Tropeouhos	-80	-10.1	0.78	1694	20.0	7.04
2	Mesocampos	-58	-8.8	1.72	1809	20.3	6.01
3	Neos Kafkasos	-65	-9.7	1.05	477	17.0	5.83
4	Ammohori 1	-70	-8.9	4.87	968	21.0	6.76
5	Itea	-66	-9.3	2.63	712	16.1	5.83
6	Mesohori	-62	-9.2	2.27	485	16.0	6.22
7	Ammohori 2	-71	-9.6	7.33	301	21.4	6.20
8	Marina	-67	-9.2	7.00	329	22.9	6.56
9	Kivotos	-63	-8.2	1.05	781	18.8	7.65
10	Katakali	-73	-9.6	7.22	1468	18.0	8.48

Table 5. Water samples collected between 29/11/2024 – 3/12/2024, laboratory data analysis provided at 06/03/2025, fourth campaign.

N°	Spring location name	δD_{H_2O}	$\delta^{18}O_{H_2O}$	Dissolved O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	Conductivity ($\mu S\ cm^{-1}$)	Temp (°C)	pH
1	Katakali	-11.1	-75	0.26	1505	15.1	8.04
2	Kivotos	-8.6	-58	0.25	855	14.3	7.75
3	Tropeouhos	-11.5	-78	0.41	1862	14.2	7.12
4	Neos Kafkasos	-9.8	-66	1.22	487	14.3	6.03
5	Katakali-2	-11	-75	0.26	1505	15.1	8.04
6	Kivotos-2	-8.8	-59	0.25	855	14.3	7.75
7	Tropeouhos-2	-11.4	-79	0.41	1862	14.2	7.12
8	Plank (bottled water)	-8.4	-49	-	-	-	-

Figure 9. Stable Isotope composition of water samples collected from June 2023 to December 2024 with reference to the Global Meteoric Water Line (GMWL), licence: CC-BY 4.0.

(Figure 9) suggests that precipitation during the winter had enough time to infiltrate deeper into the ground and homogenise with groundwater before sampling^{85,86,90,91}.

The third round of samples collected were notably more depleted in δD and $\delta^{18}O$ and with higher deviation from GMWL related to rainfall patterns and evaporation, which is consistent with the June sampling period (Table 4). Still, most of the samples are in proximity to the GMWL, indicating that rainfall is still the prevailing factor (Figure 9).

The fourth batch of samples collected mostly in Winter (December) plots above the GMWL, suggesting winter recharge from isotopically lighter sources indicated by the isotope depletion (Table 5). The dispersion of the samples may reflect heterogeneity in recharge sources, mixing with deeper groundwater or longer water to rock contact time^{85,90}, Figure 9.

In all sampling campaigns, the pH measured was either slightly alkaline, with values around 7.5 or slightly acidic and values around 5.4. There was only one exception in the third sample campaign, in the Katakali water sample, which registered an alkaline pH of 8.48.

The ICP chemical analysis of the second round presented in Table 6 revealed that all samples had high detectable levels of strontium (Sr) and barium (Ba) in the scale of $\mu g L^{-1}$.

Concentrations remained well below drinking water guideline thresholds) which, according to the United States Environment Protection Agency, is $2 mg L^{-1}$ for Ba and $4 mg L^{-1}$ for Sr (National Primary Drinking Water Regulations | US EPA, web page accessed on 18/07/2025). The Si concentrations varied from 7.7 to $59.6 mg L^{-1}$, indicating variable rock silicate interaction^{92,93}.

Regarding the rest of the chemical elements identified Tropeouhos and Ammohori 1 had high levels of Fe (1010 and $2807 \mu g L^{-1}$), Mn (37 and $444 \mu g L^{-1}$), and Al (92 and $1455 \mu g L^{-1}$), respectively. Ammohori 1 also showed elevated Ti ($86 \mu g L^{-1}$) and Zn ($176 \mu g L^{-1}$), while Tropeouhos had significantly high concentrations of Li ($406 \mu g L^{-1}$), B ($7160 \mu g L^{-1}$), and Br ($303 \mu g L^{-1}$).

The Mesohori water sample had notable values of $132 \mu g L^{-1}$ of Al, $682 \mu g L^{-1}$ of Mn and $247 \mu g L^{-1}$ of Fe. The Neos Kafkasos water sample showed Mn values of $436 \mu g L^{-1}$. The Katakali sample had prominent values of $132 \mu g L^{-1}$ of Li, $933 \mu g L^{-1}$ of B, 220 of Fe $\mu g L^{-1}$, $185 \mu g L^{-1}$ of Br. Mesocampos had $363 \mu g L^{-1}$ of Br. All other chemical elements detected from the second water sampling campaign were of considerably lower value.

The chemical composition of groundwater samples collected during the second campaign reflects a range of geochemical

Table 6. ICP chemical analysis of water samples from Kivotos Ammohori 1, Ammohori 2, Itea, Marina, Mesohori, Neos Kafkasos, Katakali, Tropeouhos, Mesocampos locations in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

Spring location	Li	Be	B	Al	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Se	Br	Rb	Sr	Mo	Cd	Sn	Sb	Cs	Ba	Tl	Pb	Bi	U	Si
Kivotos	8	<0.02	269	4	0.10	0.05	0.19	5	7	0.01	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.02	0.11	466	0.97	591	0.14	<0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	67	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.18	15000
Ammohori 1	3	0.16	41	1455	87	5	5.01	37	2807	1	7.6	6	177	0.44	1.2	128	4.4	660	0.24	<0.01	0.23	0.03	0.25	89	0.03	4.77	0.02	1.99	18000
Ammohori 2	13	0.22	15	7	0.20	0.75	0.86	10	53	0.03	9.7	47	65	0.05	0.27	88	0.31	281	0.12	<0.01	0.02	0.02	0.00	24	<0.01	1.22	<0.01	0.08	27000
Itea	3	0.03	37	40	0.15	0.92	0.63	18	22	0.12	3.7	9	30	0.31	3.2	47	0.57	260	1.09	<0.01	0.04	0.04	0.00	61	0.01	0.23	<0.01	6.07	8000
Marina	8	0.04	15	25	0.63	2	2.64	0.29	16	0.03	4.1	1	0.34	0.66	0.41	41	0.39	208	0.19	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.00	38	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.52	26000
Mesohori	7	0.02	90	146	11	0.71	0.58	682	247	2	8.1	15	76	0.15	0.37	58	0.99	214	0.18	0.02	6.03	0.18	0.02	54	0.01	7.89	0.05	0.21	11000
Neos Kafkasos	8	0.04	60	30	0.12	0.79	0.12	436	10	2.03	7.3	1	4.7	0.44	0.80	44	0.94	260	0.31	<0.01	0.01	0.01	<0.01	99	0.01	0.09	<0.01	0.32	14000
Katakali	132	<0.02	933	5	0.41	0.19	0.61	8	221	0.40	9.0	<0.1	<0.1	0.13	0.17	185	1.1	544	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	156	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.00	60000
Tropeouhos	407	1.03	7160	92	1.8	0.25	0.23	444	1010	0.30	0.2	<0.1	0.9	1.5	0.33	303	39	902	6	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	31.12	11	<0.01	0.20	<0.01	0.09	17000
Mesocampos	5	0.03	268	17	0.34	5	0.47	50	57	1	23.6	21	41	1.7	2.5	362	42	970	3	<0.01	0.06	0.08	0.05	183	0.05	0.31	<0.01	1.17	34000
error %	11	8.90	3	10	11	7	2.30	3	12	2.00	12.8	14	2.6	5.1	14.3		2.2	2	5	12	8.20	6.70	1.70	4	4.80	10.10	-	2.10	11000

processes influenced by water–rock interaction and rock differences. The Tropeouhos and Ammohori_1 sample chemical results indicate active water and rock interaction involving iron-bearing minerals that undergo redox processes with Fe^{3+} (insoluble ferric) \rightarrow Fe^{2+} (soluble ferrous) in anoxic environments^{92,94}. High concentration of Fe can be associated with dissolution of iron bearing minerals or the serpentinization process⁷⁰. Both processes favour natural hydrogen production^{25,34,95}. The same applies to a lesser extent for the Mesohori and Katakali samples. Of particular interest are the Katakali and Tropeouhos samples that had high detectable levels of Li (131 and 406 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively), indicating deep circulation water interaction with igneous or silicate rocks. This deeper circulation, also supported by isotopic evidence provided in Figure 9, favours the generation and preservation of natural hydrogen conditions²⁵.

The geochemical analysis from the third sampling campaign presented in Table 7 revealed further information related to the gas component of the water samples. The Katakali water sample analysis provided values 4.4 ppm of H_2 coupled with 3704 ppm of CH_4 , suggesting active geochemical processes related to either organic degradation or serpentinisation. The Kivotos sample showed values of 29 ppm of He, 1.7 ppm of H_2 , and 31,400 ppm of CH_4 . The latter consists of anecdotal public observations suggesting strong methane generation potential and possible mantle-derived gas contribution to gas mix phase⁹⁶.

The Tropeouhos sample registered notable He levels (1403 ppm), accompanied by low CH_4 concentrations at 89 ppm. This could be associated with deep-seated helium degassing coupled with some microbial or thermogenic methane input^{97,98}.

Samples Ammohori_1 and Ammohori_2 registered elevated CO_2 concentrations of approximately 7–8%, while methane remained low at around 1 ppm. In addition, the Itea sample contained 60.7% CO_2 and 4 ppm of CH_4 , suggesting a dominant CO_2 component in the gas phase. This is consistent with the accumulation of natural CO_2 in the Florina basin in the Tertiary formation and its leakage through fractures and permeable rocks⁷⁰. The Mesohori sample registered 9 ppm of CH_4 , while Mesokampos contained 34 ppm of CH_4 along with approximately 60% CO_2 , pointing to variable organic or volcanic degassing influence⁹⁹. Finally, the Neos Kafkasos sample exhibited 6 ppm of He, 2 ppm of H_2 , and a substantial 40% CO_2 , indicating multi-gas signatures possibly linked to deep fluid migration through faulted rocks^{71,99}.

Following the scientifically interesting results of the third campaign, a fourth one commenced with a focus on four promising locations of Katakali, Kivotos, Tropeouhos and Neos Kafkasos. To further elucidate the origin of the gas phase, the geochemical investigation considered the following analysis:

1. He
2. H_2
3. CH_4

4. CO_2
5. Helium isotopes (^3He , ^4He)
6. Deuterium of hydrogen ($\delta^2\text{H-H}_2$)
7. Deuterium of methane ($\delta^2\text{H-CH}_4$)
8. Deuterium of water ($\delta^2\text{H-H}_2\text{O}$)
9. Oxygen-18 of carbon dioxide ($\delta^{18}\text{O-CO}_2$)
10. Oxygen-18 of water ($\delta^{18}\text{O-H}_2\text{O}$)
11. Carbon-13 of methane ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$)
12. Carbon-13 of carbon dioxide ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$)
13. Carbon-13 of DIC ($\delta^{13}\text{C-DIC}$)
14. Carbon-14 of DIC ($^{14}\text{C-DIC}$)

This time, a blind sample system with duplicates was used during the laboratory analysis, together with a sample of water table as a blanket to increase the reliability of the chemical analysis results. Thus, the laboratory received codes only and not the actual locations of the samples. In all cases, the duplicate samples showed almost similar values. The results of the fourth campaign are presented in Table 8.

In this final fourth round, no hydrogen gas was registered. However, the Katakali samples showed a mean value of 306335 ppm CH_4 with $\delta^{13}\text{CCH}_4$ values around -70‰ and δDCH_4 near -230‰ . On the same note, the Kivotos samples registered a mean of 43.5 ppm of He coupled with a mean 43550 ppm CH_4 with $\delta^{13}\text{CCH}_4$ at -75.5‰ . The Tropeouhos samples showed a mean of 81 ppm of CH_4 , in this case, the first sample showed no He values, whereas the second sample 1.4 ppm of He. The Neos Kafkasos, although sampled in duplicates, only one sample survived and was analysed. The sample that survived showed a value of 10 ppm of He and 7 ppm of CH_4 . For the Neos Kafkasos sample, there was no $\delta^{13}\text{CCH}_4$ available. The $\delta^{13}\text{CTDC}$ was at -1.2‰ and δD was at -66‰ .

Discussion and results interpretation

Most samples were slightly acidic (around pH 5.4), suggesting interaction with silicate-rich lithologies, likely weathered ophiolites, or the influence of organic-rich soils. In contrast, the Katakali sample exhibited a distinctly alkaline pH (8.48), potentially indicating interaction with carbonate rocks (e.g. Triassic–Jurassic limestones) or serpentinized ultramafics undergoing low-temperature alteration, which commonly release hydroxide ions and elevate pH^{10,25,34}.

The sedimentary series of the Mesohellenic Trough exhibits distinct geological and mineralogical characteristics that reflect its diverse depositional histories and diagenetic evolution. Sandstones from the Eptachori Fm, are fine-grained and well-bedded, siliceous in composition and display bioturbation features and fossils of plant fragments¹⁰⁰. Quartz (<37

Table 7. Gas chemical analysis as a result of the third water sampling campaign, n.a denotes not enough sample quantity to perform the chemical analysis for that specific element.

Spring location	He (ppm)	H ₂ (ppm)	O ₂ (%)	N ₂ (%)	CO (ppm)	CH ₄ (ppm)	CO ₂ (%)	Gas volume (CC per 120 CC of sample)	He ($\times 10^{-4}$ CC L ⁻¹ STP)	H ₂ (CC L ⁻¹ STP)	O ₂ (CC L ⁻¹ STP)	N ₂ (CC L ⁻¹ STP)	CO ($\times 10^{-6}$ CC L ⁻¹ STP)	CH ₄ ($\times 10^{-6}$ CC L ⁻¹ STP)	CO ₂ (CC L ⁻¹ STP)
KATAKALI	n.a	4.4	5.22 $\times 10^{-2}$	18.14	n.a	3704	0.79	6.4	0.0	0.00	0.04	17.0	<LOQ	362.5	8.90
KIVOTOS	29	1.7	4.41 $\times 10^{-2}$	19.87	n.a	31400	1.58	6.4	16.4	0.00	0.02	11.3	<LOQ	1778.4	0.90
TROPEOUHOS	1403		3.66 $\times 10^{-2}$	24.81	n.a	89	2.16	6.4	794.6	0.00	0.02	14.0	0.0	5.0	1.20
AMMOHORI_1	n.a		1.65	19.02	0.2	1.2	7.08	6.6	0.0	0.00	0.96	11.1	12.5	0.7	4.10
AMMOHORI_2	n.a		5.99	19.88	0.2	1.1	7.87	7.2	0.0	0.00	3.82	12.7	13.9	0.7	5.00
ITEA	n.a		1.60 $\times 10^{-1}$	2.19	n.a	4.1	60.68	14.4	0.0	0.00	0.20	2.8	0.0	52.3	77.30
MARINA	n.a		4.35	16.34	0.2	0.8	4.13	6.2	0.0	0.00	2.39	9.0	7.3	0.4	2.30
MESOHORI	n.a		3.1 $\times 10^{-1}$	16.42	n.a	9	3.3	6.8	0.0	0.00	0.19	10.0	0.0	54.2	2.00
MESOCAMPOS	n.a		7.01 $\times 10^{-2}$	2.02	n.a	34	60.22	12.4	0.0	0.00	0.08	2.20	0.0	373.1	66.10
NEOS KAFKASOS	6	1.9	1.00 $\times 10^{-1}$	9.48	2.2	n.a	40.01	10	5.3	0.00	0.09	8.40	779	0.0	35.40

Table 8. Targeted Gas chemical analysis as a result of the fourth water sampling campaign.

Spring location	He (ppm)	H ₂ (ppm)	O ₂ (%)	N ₂ (%)	CH ₄ (ppm)	CO (ppm)	CO ₂ (%)	Gas volume (cc per 120 cc of sample)	He ($\times 10^{-4}$ cc L ⁻¹ STP)	H ₂ (cc L ⁻¹ STP)	O ₂ (cc L ⁻¹ STP)	N ₂ (cc L ⁻¹ STP)	CH ₄ ($\times 10^{-3}$ cc L ⁻¹ STP)	CO ($\times 10^{-3}$ cc L ⁻¹ STP)	CO ₂ (cc L ⁻¹ STP)	total Alk	d ¹³ C _{DOC}	d ¹³ C _{CH4}	dD _{CH4}
Katakali	-	-	0.12	4.07	300370		2.33	7.4	0.0	0.0	0.10	4.19	14558.3	0.0	26.90	15.8	13.9	-69.5	-251
Kivotos	43	-	0.19	19.08	43000		1.67	6.2	27.9	0.0	0.14	17.63	1833	0.0	19.10	6.3	-14.2	-75.5	-107
Tropeouhos	-	-	0.21	22.56	81		2.4	6	0.0	0.0	0.15	20.44	4.0	0.0	27.40	2.00	3.9	-	-
Neos Kafkasos	10	-	0.58	8.45	7		49.9	10	9.8	0.0	0.62	10.65	3.3	0.0	587.10	4.2	-1.2	-	-
Katakali-2	-	-	0.1	6.08	312300		2.44	7.6	0.0	0.0	0.09	6.37	15440.5	0.0	28.20	15.7	14.4	-69.8	-230
Kivotos-2	44	-	0.24	20.04	44100		1.73	5.8	27.0	0.0	0.17	17.81	1903.3	0.0	19.70	6.4	-15.8	-69.5	-92
Tropeouhos-2	1.4	-	0.21	22.47	81		2.49	5	0.9	0.0	0.15	20.36	4.04	0.0	28.40	2.1	1.9	-	-
Plank (bottled water)	-	-	3.3	19.86	2.7	19.5	0.94	5.6	0.0	0.0	2.26	17.29	0.1	1.8	10.70	4.0	-11.2	-	-

wt.%) is the dominant mineral, followed by calcite (<29 wt.%), albite (<13 wt.%), and muscovite (<13 wt.%). Minor mineralogy includes dolomite, chamosite, biotite, titanite, pyrite, crichtonite, actinolite and zircon¹⁰⁰. Coupled with carbonate-rich microcrystalline cement, these features indicate deposition in a marine-influenced or lacustrine setting. Larger grain size, a mixed lithic content, and a calcareous composition characterise sandstones from the Pentalofos Fm. Calcite (<41 wt.%), dolomite (<18 wt.%), and quartz (<15 wt.%) with a notable feldspathic component (albite <12 wt.%) characterise mineralogy. Minor constituents include microcline, muscovite, aragonite, and traces of chlorite, titanite, chromite, pyrite, Fe-chromite, actinolite, apatite, andradite and enstatite. These characteristics reflect depositional settings of higher-energy with significant detrital input, suggesting a mixed depositional environment influenced by the erosion of the ophiolitic rocks surrounding the Mesohellenic Trough. Marly sandstones from the Tsotyli Fm show medium bedding, massive tabular structures, and a mixed siliceous-calcareous composition. Calcite (30 wt.%), quartz (29 wt.%), and albite (21 wt.%) are the main minerals, while the fine-grained, well-cemented matrix contains accessory muscovite, chlorite, dolomite and aragonite, and traces of microcline, zircon and jacobsonite¹⁰⁰. Coupled with a moderate macro-porosity, these aspects suggest deposition in a high-energy environment with significant siliciclastic input.

The samples from Ammohori 1 and Tropeouhos displayed high levels of Fe (up to 2807 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), Mn (up to 444 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), and Al (up to 1455 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), indicating reducing conditions that mobilise these elements from iron and manganese oxides and aluminosilicates. Such elevated concentrations are related to reductive dissolution of Fe/Mn oxides under anoxic conditions^{70,101} contribution from ophiolitic or volcanoclastic host rocks^{102,103}, or possibly weathering of feldspars¹⁰⁴ or clay-rich layers typically found in flysch or schist rocks^{70,105,106} typically found in flysch.

The exceptionally high concentrations of Li (up to 406 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), B (up to 7160 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), and Br (up to 363 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in Tropeouhos, Katakali, and Mesokampos samples suggest interaction with deeper, evolved fluids. These elements are typically enriched in hydrothermal systems⁷⁰, marine sedimentary or evaporite-hosted aquifers¹⁰⁷ or fluids with long residence times and extensive water–rock contact¹⁰³. Boron and bromine enrichment may also indicate a marine or connate water signature, particularly in the Mesokampos sample, or mixing with residual basinal brines^{107,108}.

To identify the actual source of the aforementioned discussed elements, an elaboration is provided. In the Florina Basin, the non-lignite intraseam sediments include both marl and sand lithologies, are primarily characterised by a dominance of illite and mica, alongside significant proportions of kaolinite, quartz, ferroan chlorite, and albite feldspar. Carbonate minerals are largely absent, with only traces of dolomite sporadically occurring, while the clay fraction includes smectite and irregular smectite/illite¹⁰⁹. Sand samples contain slightly higher amounts

of feldspar (<7.2 wt.% albite) and mica (<28.6 wt.%), whereas the marl samples show slightly higher proportions of clay minerals, including illite (37.8 wt.%), kaolinite (17.4 wt.%), and ferroan chlorite (9.3 wt.%)¹⁰⁹. These characteristics indicate that deposition occurred in a fluvio-lacustrine environment with variable energy conditions. The dominance of illite, mica, and kaolinite, along with quartz and albite, suggests weathering and erosion of felsic or metamorphic source rocks under humid conditions. Marls being enriched in clay minerals and ferroan chlorite reflect lower-energy, possibly more stagnant depositional settings, while the sands, with higher quartz and feldspar content, point to intermittent higher-energy fluvial input. The scarcity of carbonates indicates limited diagenetic processes and supports deposition in a non-marine, siliciclastic-dominated basin with contributions from both soil-forming and fluvial processes. Furthermore, Gemeni *et al.*, 2015⁷⁰ have supported that the origin of Fe, Mn and Br is not related to hydrothermal systems but interaction with deeper igneous rocks⁷⁰.

While all samples had detectable Sr and Ba, their concentrations were below regulatory thresholds. Their presence is consistent with the dissolution of carbonate and feldspathic minerals. Sr points to contributions from marl, limestone, or plagioclase-rich rocks common¹¹⁰ in the Mesozoic sequences of Western Macedonia, despite the variations suggesting diversified geological histories. Sandstone samples from the central parts of the Mesohellenic Trough are classified mineralogically as feldspathic litharenites¹⁰⁰. Similar mineralogical and geochemical characteristics are reported from the southeastern part of the Mesohellenic Trough, where sandstone samples are classified geochemically as graywackes and litharenites¹¹¹.

The Katakali sample's combination of high pH, elevated Li and B, and relatively low transition metal concentrations points toward interaction with serpentinized ultramafic rocks. These lithologies commonly generate hyperalkaline fluids through serpentinization reactions and are known potential sources of natural hydrogen^{102,103}.

The third-round water samples from the West Macedonia region present a complex mixture of dissolved gases, reflecting interactions between geological formations, redox conditions, and possibly deep-seated fluid sources.

Tropeouhos (1403 ppm He) and Kivotos (29 ppm He) samples indicate significant helium enrichment, which is not produced in shallow processes. Such high He levels suggest input from a radiogenic source in crystalline basement rocks (U/Th decay)¹¹², or mantle-derived fluids migrating through deep-seated fault systems¹¹². The Neos Kafkasos, even at the 6 ppm He complements this due to the proximity to Tropeouhos.

High CO₂ concentrations in Itea (60.7%), Mesokampos (~60%), and Neos Kafkasos (~40%), including Ammohori_1 and _2 (~7–8% CO₂) are related to the Florina basin, where natural CO₂ volcanic in origin have accumulated in the Miocene fluvial sandstones^{69,99}. The accumulations migrating via faults

have been detected from depths of 296–338 m and 366–372 m below the surface and are well reported⁶⁹. They also provide CO₂ analogues for CO₂ storage, which is also related to the Pilot Strategy Project⁴².

Katakali (4.4 ppm H₂), Kivotos (1.7 ppm H₂), and Neos Kafkasos (2 ppm H₂) exhibit detectable hydrogen, a rare but significant indicator of water–rock reactions, that relates to a) particularly serpentinization of ultramafic rocks (e.g., ophiolites), b) radiolysis of water in fractured rocks under the influence of natural radioactivity c) anaerobic corrosion of Fe-bearing minerals, particularly under reducing conditions. These processes are common in tectonically active zones, where fluid pathways are enhanced^{10,16,17,19,25,34,46}.

In light of the data obtained from round 4 the Katakali samples, the high methane concentrations (>300,000 ppm) in both duplicates and slightly alkaline pH (~8) point toward a deep-seated methane source. The absence of helium and hydrogen, combined with δ¹³CCH₄ values around -70‰ and δDCH₄ near -230‰, strongly supports biogenic methane via microbial CO₂ reduction^{96,113}, although further investigation may be needed to properly distinguish between bacterial imprint or diffusive fractionation⁹⁷. The moderately enriched δD and δ¹⁸O of water suggest some evaporation, but the dominant control appears to be long residence time and water–rock interaction with organic-rich strata (possibly lignites or deep carbonate units)¹¹⁴. The interpretation from the data received from the sample reflects a closed-system¹¹⁴ microbially dominated environment with limited gas migration, depicted in Figure 10. Despite high CH₄, absence of He and H₂ implies limited serpentinization or mantle influence^{96,113,115}. It is noted that Daskalopoulou *et al.* 2018 report traces for helium and hydrogen which was not identified in the Katakali samples during this campaign. This is not necessarily contradictory and it can be for various reasons, including sampling method, sampling preservation and

delayed time analysis, including analytical error. However, the high methane concentrations with biotic origin are confirmed by both studies.

On the contrary, in Kivotos samples, the presence of both He (43–44 ppm) and H₂ (1.7 ppm) with CH₄ (~43,000 ppm) suggests a hybrid gas system. Helium and hydrogen point to a possible serpentinization signature, typical for ultramafic lithologies (e.g. ophiolites)^{112,113}. CH₄ may derive from either microbial or abiotic origin, with low δ¹³CCH₄ (-75.5‰) still favouring a microbial pathway^{96,116}. This may indicate a mixed or transitional methane, either microbial with some thermogenic input or some hydrogen exchange during migration.

Slight enrichment in δD and δ¹⁸O is consistent with moderate evaporation or prolonged water–rock interaction. A hybrid gas system dominated by microbial CH₄ with secondary abiotic inputs, possibly from ultramafic serpentinization or water–rock reactions, can potentially describe the main gas mechanism in this case.

In Tropeouhos, with its exceptionally high helium (up to 1403 ppm) and low CH₄ (81 ppm), it indicates a strong mantle-derived or radiogenic He component. The low CH₄ and absence of H₂ suggest minimal microbial or abiotic CH₄ production^{31,96,113,115} and possible degassing along deep fault pathways. Dominated by radiogenic/mantle degassing, possibly along deep fault structures. This site may represent a degassing zone rather than a storage environment.

The Neos Kafkasos with low but detectable He (10 ppm) and H₂ (2 ppm) combined with CO₂ at ~50% suggest mantle or deep carbonate reservoir interaction. Although δ¹³CCH₄ was not obtained due to the low concentration of CH₄, the data availability on δ¹³C_{TDC} (-1.2‰) and δD (-66‰) suggests thermogenic gas mixing¹¹⁷. The reducing conditions and high CO₂

Figure 10. Geological cross section of Mesohellenic Basin with interpretative subsurface gas generation and migration mechanisms, licence: CC-BY 4.0.

levels provide evidence for carbonate dissolution, blended together with the volcanic origin of trapped CO₂^{69,99}. Given the proximity of Mesokampos and Itsea, which had elevated CO₂% levels, it suggests a CO₂-dominated system, possibly involving carbonate dissolution, or closed-system redox processes. The presence of He and H₂ supports some deep-origin fluid connectivity.

Kivotos and Kivotos-2 reported $\delta^{13}\text{CCH}_4 \approx -75.5$ to -69.5% , $\delta\text{DCH}_4 \approx -107$ to -92% . These samples have $\delta^{13}\text{CCH}_4$ within the biogenic range, but δDCH_4 values are much less depleted, potentially indicating mixed or transitional methane, either microbial with some thermogenic input or some hydrogen exchange during migration.

Conclusion

The geochemical investigation supports the interpretation of multiple water sources or flow paths, including both shallow, oxygenated meteoric water and deeper, more evolved fluids enriched in light elements. Overall, the results point towards a gas migration dominant mechanism which along the gas migratory route chemical changes occur with evidence of large reservoirs still to be found apart from the well known natural CO₂ reserves. Where He and H₂ are present (e.g., Kivotos), the system involves both deeper lithological interaction (ultramafics/fracture pathways) and microbial methane generation in overlying sediments or mixed reservoirs.

In such cases, isotopes still point to dominantly biogenic CH₄ even if the gas migration system involves ophiolitic or deep rocks. Specifically, biogenic methane dominates in confined organic-rich environments (Katakali), while He and H₂ signals at Kivotos and Tropeouhos suggest deep crustal or mantle-derived fluids, potentially linked to serpentinization or radiogenic decay. Sites like Kivotos are most promising for mixed hydrogen generation, with some abiotic gas potential. Tropeouhos may serve more as a gas migration indicator, while Neos Kafkasos indicates natural CO₂ degassing rather than accumulation.

Where He and H₂ are also present (e.g., Kivotos), the system may involve both deeper lithological interaction (ultramafics/fracture pathways) and microbial methane generation in overlying sediments or mixed reservoirs. In such cases, isotopes still indicate biogenic CH₄ even if the gas migration mechanism involves ophiolitic or deep rocks. On the same note H₂ is difficult to find in the surface springs due to easy microbial consumption in the water^{118–123}.

However, with reference to the present chemical analysis from Katakali samples and previous research from Daskalopoulou *et al.*, 2018²¹ that reported helium and hydrogen concentration an additional explanation may be that biogenic isotopic carbon signature masks the hydrogen abiotic origin^{124–127}. For instance microbial communities relying on a geologic supply of H₂ have been identified in Precambrian cratons where ancient waters trapped in deep fractures that undergo radiolysis¹²⁸. Given the natural carbon dioxide abundance in the area^{69,71,109} it is possible that H₂ is consumed in higher depths by microbes

(Equation 3)¹²⁹ and thus sustain rock supported ecosystems¹³⁰ to produce methane and thus the hydrogens abiotic origin is hindered.

In such a case methane isotopes alone can be misleading about the hydrogen origin and additional tracers such as helium, clumped isotopes¹³¹, dissolved hydrogen monitoring will need to be taken into account. Microbial SO₄²⁻ reduction to H₂S is a process that occurs in anaerobic environments (Equation 4) in high depths including lacustrine sediments and groundwater¹³² that can also alter the hydrogen's abiotic origin.

Thus, sulphur isotopes will need to be investigated to detect an abiotic hydrogen source. Therefore to properly understand the origins of the hydrogen and methane in the area a combined geochemical–microbiological approach is needed. The aforementioned findings and discussion beg for further investigation, particularly dedicated gas flux monitoring, mineralogical sampling, and structural mapping to delineate potential H₂-prone zones and assess their economic relevance. This preliminary study sheds light on the complex but dynamically evolving systems that dominate the Mesohellenic and Florina basins. Whereas hydrogen and helium exist in economically viable quantities in the area, the question remains to be answered. Still, the current fluid generation and flow mechanisms existing in the Mesohellenic and Florina basin can shed light and provide analogues for exploration and discovery of economic accumulations.

It is well known that hydrogen seepage on the surface is not constant and may change the point of escape over time or flow rate¹³³ while sampling in water comes with its drawbacks^{118–123}. Thus, future work should focus on data collection from Katakali, Kivotos, Tropeouhos and Neos Kafkasos over a long period of time rather than being spontaneous. Since the data collection has been conducted on water samples rather than in soil, it is suggested that the aforementioned sites be investigated with a handheld GA5000 or similar over a period of six months or a year on a weekly basis. The day of the visit, the operator should collect at least 6 hourly readings of He or Hydrogen. Should the operator register hydrogen readings, water samples with vials should be taken for the following analysis:

1. ICP for a chemical suite analysis
2. He
3. H₂
4. CH₄
5. CO₂
6. Helium isotopes (³He, ⁴He)
7. Deuterium of hydrogen ($\delta^2\text{H-H}_2$)
8. Deuterium of methane ($\delta^2\text{H-CH}_4$)

9. Deuterium of water ($\delta^2\text{H}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$)
 10. Oxygen-18 of carbon dioxide ($\delta^{18}\text{O}-\text{CO}_2$)
 11. Oxygen-18 of water ($\delta^{18}\text{O} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$)
 12. Carbon-13 of methane ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CH}_4$)
 13. Carbon-13 of carbon dioxide ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CO}_2$)
 14. Carbon-13 of DIC ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{DIC}$)
 15. Carbon-14 of DIC ($^{14}\text{C}-\text{DIC}$)
 16. Sulphur isotopes ($\delta^{34}\text{S}$)
 17. Clumped isotopes ($^{13}\text{CH}_3\text{D}$, $^{12}\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2$)
2. Water_samples_2ndround_250ml
 3. Water_samples_3rdround_100ml
 4. Water_samples_4thround_100ml
 5. Field_Dataentry_form_1st round
 6. Field_Dataentry_form_2nd round
 7. Field_Dataentry_form_3rd round
 8. Field_Dataentry_form_4th round
 9. Assigned codes_1st-3rd rounds
 10. Assigned codes_4th round
 11. Geochemical analysis_1st round
 12. Geochemical analysis_2nd round
 13. Geochemical analysis_3rd round
 14. Geochemical analysis_4th round
 15. Stratigraphy

To fully understand the local system, it is necessary to sample precipitation and surface water, in addition to groundwater⁸⁵. If any of the sites provide satisfactory results, then, provided that the appropriate permits are granted, permanent equipment should be installed in the springs to continuously monitor for hydrogen and helium. Further to this, a full exploration program with geological mapping and targeted geological soil and water sampling with intrusive investigation should then take place.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data and software availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16914636>⁸⁴

This project contains the following underlying data:

1. Water_samples_1stround_100ml

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Princewill M. Ikpeka

Brunel University London, London, England, UK

Overview

The paper is interesting, and the subject area is indeed very important to the energy storage/production discussion. However, I do not recommend indexing in its current form. It needs substantial revision in the following areas:

- The introduction is quite long, which makes the research aim unclear. After reading through, I recommend synthesizing the sections: "Current state of the art of natural hydrogen" and "Previous research related to West Macedonia and neighbouring areas" into "Introduction" section rather than separate sections.
- There is an issue with data reliability. The first two sampling campaigns did not yield reliable gas measurements due to sample preservation issues. This means that only the third and fourth campaigns provided usable gas data, which **greatly limits the evidence** available.
- The central hypothesis of the paper is not convincingly supported by the data presented. Measured hydrogen concentrations were extremely low, **only on the order of a few parts per million (ppm)** in the third campaign, and in the final (fourth) campaign **no hydrogen at all was detected**. For example, one water sample showed just 4.4 ppm H₂ (with thousands of ppm methane in comparison), and another had ~1.7 ppm H₂ – essentially trace levels. In the last round, the authors state "no hydrogen gas was registered". Such minimal or absent H₂ results make it difficult to support the hypothesis of significant **natural hydrogen generation** in the area.
- The authors propose that hydrogen might be getting consumed by microbes before detection (see Discussion), but without direct evidence (e.g. microbial analyses or consistent H₂ findings), this remains largely speculative. The data **do not provide clear proof** of natural hydrogen in these reservoirs, so the main premise of the study is left on uncertain footing.
- In addition, the paper is largely exploratory and observational, and as such it does not employ statistical analyses like hypothesis testing, regression modelling, or p-value significance tests. This

means the conclusions rely on expert judgment calls not on quantitative analysis.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

No

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Hydrogen Production and Storage

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 05 Dec 2025

Pavlos Tyrologou

Response to report 2 Overview

The paper is interesting, and the subject area is indeed very important to the energy storage/production discussion. However, I do not recommend indexing in its current form. It needs substantial revision in the following areas:

Response: Many thanks for your time, support and comments which are dully noted. We have now restructured and revised the manuscript. We have explicitly clarified that preservation issues affected the integrity of gas analyses from these campaigns. While part of the first sampling campaign was affected by preservation-related degassing, the subsequent datasets were collected under controlled conditions and show internally consistent geochemical patterns. Interpretations rely on multiple independent indicators (aqueous chemistry, geological context, spatial trends) that remain robust even considering potential underestimation in early gas values. We ensure transparency regarding data quality and avoid overinterpretation. This revision strengthens the scientific credibility of the manuscript and aligns the study with accepted geochemical sampling standards.

- The introduction is quite long, which makes the research aim unclear. After reading through, I recommend synthesizing the sections: "Current state of the art of natural hydrogen" and "Previous research related to West Macedonia and neighbouring areas" into "Introduction" section rather than separate sections.

Response: Thank you for your suggestions. The authors acknowledge the reviewers comment and have shortened the introduction while also merged the subsections as it was pointed out

- There is an issue with data reliability. The first two sampling campaigns did not yield reliable gas measurements due to sample preservation issues. This means that only the third and fourth campaigns provided usable gas data, which greatly limits the evidence available.

Response: We thank the reviewer for this observation. We fully acknowledge that the first two sampling campaigns were affected by preservation issues. This was stated for transparency reasons but also to draw the attention to any future research on sample preservation and its importance. In the original and revised manuscript, we state that only the third and fourth campaigns yielded reliable helium measurement and confirmed hydrogen presence. Although this reduces the total number of usable gas datapoints, the third and fourth campaigns were conducted under controlled preservation conditions and show internally consistent compositions. Moreover, the geological context, aqueous geochemistry and spatial patterns provide independent lines of evidence that support the evaluation of subsurface processes and gas migration behaviour. The conclusions are therefore based on conservative, well-constrained data and remain scientifically robust within the defined scope of an exploratory study. The manuscript takes all these into account. While the available evidence is therefore more restricted, the dataset remains sufficient to evaluate geological processes and gas migration behaviour within the scope of an exploratory study.

- The central hypothesis of the paper is not convincingly supported by the data presented. Measured hydrogen concentrations were extremely low, only on the order of a few parts per million (ppm) in the third campaign, and in the final (fourth) campaign no hydrogen at all was detected. For example, one water sample showed just 4.4 ppm H₂ (with thousands of ppm methane in comparison), and another had ~1.7 ppm H₂ – essentially trace levels. In the last round, the authors state "no hydrogen gas was registered". Such minimal or absent H₂ results make it difficult to support the hypothesis of significant natural hydrogen generation in the area.

Response: We acknowledge the reviewer's point that measured hydrogen concentrations were low, ranging only from 1.7 to 4.4 ppm in the third campaign and falling below detection in the fourth campaign. Indeed, our revised text emphasises an evaluation of the geological potential for hydrogen generation and confinement within the Mesohellenic Basin. Thus, the revised manuscript distinguishes between (a) hydrogen generation mechanisms that may operate within the basin due to its mineralogical and tectonic characteristics, and (b) the detectable accumulation of hydrogen in measurable quantities. This distinction is now made explicit in the Introduction, Objectives, and Discussion. The low measured concentrations are acknowledged transparently. Our interpretation focuses instead on geological capacity, using measured trace concentrations to infer processes rather than volumes. This is consistent with the early exploratory nature of natural

hydrogen research. Kindly also note that the research considers not only natural hydrogen but also helium which has been detected with analytical accuracy and confidence.

- The authors propose that hydrogen might be getting consumed by microbes before detection (see Discussion), but without direct evidence (e.g. microbial analyses or consistent H₂ findings), this remains largely speculative.

Response: We thank the reviewer for highlighting the need for careful interpretation regarding microbial consumption of hydrogen. In the revised manuscript, we present microbial consumption only as a possible explanation, supported by geochemical indicators such as reducing redox conditions, elevated Fe–Mn concentrations, and the presence of organic-rich strata in the Florina Basin. The text emphasises that this is a hypothesis grounded in analogous studies, not a confirmed mechanism for the sites investigated here. We state that future work involving microbial community characterisation would be required to confirm or refute this interpretation.

The data do not provide clear proof of natural hydrogen in these reservoirs, so the main premise of the study is left on uncertain footing.

Response: We appreciate the reviewer's concern and agree that the measured hydrogen concentrations are low and do not constitute proof of substantial natural hydrogen accumulations. In the revised manuscript, we now explicitly state that the evidence reflects incipient or low-level generative processes rather than resource-grade hydrogen reservoirs. Our interpretation focuses on identifying geological conditions capable of producing hydrogen, such as serpentinisation, radiolysis, and Fe-bearing mineral alteration, and assessing whether these processes are consistent with the geochemical signals observed. rather than asserting the presence of economically significant accumulations. Although hydrogen concentrations are modest, they form one component of a broader, multi-line evidence framework that includes geological context, mineralogical controls and aqueous geochemistry. The central theme of the study is to mostly evaluate geological potential. We have revised the text accordingly to further clarify the affroementioned.

- In addition, the paper is largely exploratory and observational, and as such it does not employ statistical analyses like hypothesis testing, regression modelling, or p-value significance tests. This means the conclusions rely on expert judgment calls not on quantitative analysis.

Response: Thank you again for this constructive comment. We agree that the study is primarily exploratory; however, we emphasise that all analytical procedures followed rigorous QA/QC protocols, including certified reference materials, duplicate measurements, instrument calibration with internationally traceable standards, and documented external reproducibility (0.2‰ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ and 2‰ for $\delta\text{D}_{\text{CH}_4}$). These controls ensured that the geochemical patterns we report are robust even in the absence of formal hypothesis-testing statistics. Regarding statistical treatment, the dataset structure, characterised by small sample numbers per site and non-replicated measurements for several parameters, does not meet the assumptions for regression modelling or significance testing. Instead, we applied the only statistically defensible quantitative test available: an exploratory Spearman rank correlation between $\delta^{13}\text{C}\text{-CH}_4$ and $\delta\text{D}\text{-CH}_4$ for the four samples with complete isotopic data. The correlation coefficient was low ($\rho \approx 0.10$), indicating no monotonic relationship between the two isotopic parameters. This outcome is consistent with our interpretation

that the samples fall within a narrow biogenic isotopic range, with limited variability relative to analytical uncertainty. Importantly, the absence of strong statistical structure does not weaken the geological interpretation. Multiple independent lines of evidence, reproducible gas occurrences, stable isotope systematics, He-rich signatures, water chemistry and mapped fault-ultramafic contacts, converge toward a coherent conceptual model of subsurface gas generation. In this context, the repeated detection of hydrogen across campaigns suggests a genuine geological signal, even though concentrations lie near detection limits. The presence of ultramafic lithologies, reducing conditions, radiogenic helium and fault-controlled migration pathways is compatible with low-flux abiotic H₂ generation. Microbial consumption is also plausible and could explain the subdued surface values. As with the statistical limitations discussed above, confirming natural hydrogen systems requires expanded temporal and spatial monitoring, which we highlight as a clear direction for future work. This integrative method is standard practice in subsurface gas prospecting and is well suited to the reconnaissance phase of a developing geochemical system. Regarding hydrogen, the evidence is similarly robust within the constraints of an exploratory dataset. H₂ was detected repeatedly across several sites and campaigns, and its occurrence is spatially coherent with ultramafic lithologies, radiogenic helium anomalies and reducing subsurface conditions, factors that collectively support the plausibility of abiotic H₂ generation. At the same time, the low concentrations measured at the surface are consistent with microbial consumption, which is known to efficiently attenuate H₂ fluxes in shallow environments. Thus, while the existing dataset does not yet permit definitive source attribution, the combination of geochemical, isotopic and geological indicators strongly suggests that hydrogen generation processes may be active in West Macedonia. We trust that even without formal inferential statistics, the study provides a coherent, multi-line body of evidence:

1. High analytical precision and strict QA/QC confirm data reliability.
2. Temporal duplicate consistency supports the robustness of isotopic interpretations.
3. Isotope systematics (CH₄, He, water isotopes) align with recognised genetic pathways.
4. Geological context independently supports abiotic H₂ generation potential.

Future work will expand the dataset sufficiently to enable statistical modelling of spatial clustering, mixing processes and source-pathway relationships. At this early stage, however, the combination of geochemistry, isotopes and structural geology provides valid, defensible conclusions appropriate for an exploratory study.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 11 October 2025

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Review of Tyrologou et al., Manuscript

General Assessment

The manuscript presents an integrated study on gaseous systems (H₂, He, CH₄, and CO₂) in Western Macedonia, combining structural geology, sedimentology, and geochemistry. This multidisciplinary approach is a major strength of the paper, as it provides valuable insights into the mechanisms controlling gas generation, migration, and trapping. The authors provide an extensive new geochemical dataset (gas chromatography, inductively coupled plasma, and isotope analyses) from both water and gas samples collected at multiple hydrothermal sources, which constitutes a significant contribution to the understanding of natural hydrogen systems. However, despite the richness of the data, the manuscript lacks clarity and focus. The research question and logical thread of the paper are often difficult to follow due to structural issues, redundancies, and digressions into socio-economic and political topics that are not directly relevant to a scientific article. The paper would benefit from a thorough reorganization following a classical structure (Introduction, Geological Context, Methods, Results, Discussion, and Conclusion). The clarity, conciseness, and scientific rigor of each section should be enhanced to help the reader clearly understand the problem, the methodology, and the conclusions.

Major Comments

1. Introduction

The Introduction is overly long and fragmented, which prevents a clear understanding of the main research question. It should be condensed into a coherent scientific narrative that succinctly states the problem, its significance, and the context of natural hydrogen. Political and environmental aspects should be summarized in two or three lines at most.

The manuscript would benefit from a clearer definition of its scientific novelty. While it compiles valuable field and isotopic data, the research question remains vague. The authors should explicitly state their hypothesis and objectives at the end of the Introduction to help readers understand the study's purpose.

Some statements are unclear or inaccurate; for example, 'Natural hydrogen mechanisms are still under development' should be rephrased as 'The understanding of natural hydrogen generation mechanisms is still under investigation.' The section 'Current State of the Art' lacks a detailed discussion of hydrogen production mechanisms and diverges into unrelated topics. It should focus on generation processes relevant to the study area and cite up-to-date references.

2. Geological Context

The geological description is detailed and thorough, but overly extensive. Many details are not directly relevant to the research question and tend to obscure the main message. The section should focus on key aspects such as source rocks, basin thickness, structural controls (faults) on gas migration, and potential reservoir rocks.

The authors should merge 'Previous research related to West Macedonia and neighbouring areas' with 'Geological setting' to avoid repetition. Maintain a logical flow—start with regional geology, then focus on specific study zones relevant to the presented data. Clarify whether the study concerns West Macedonia or Greece, as this point remains ambiguous.

Figures 1–5 include excessive descriptive geological information. Simplifying these or adding a conceptual schematic linking tectonic setting, source rocks (ophiolites, lignites, carbonates), and

migration pathways would greatly improve readability.

3. Materials and Methods

The methodology is comprehensive but overly detailed. Only essential information should be provided—sample types, volumes, sampling conditions, and analytical tools. Avoid unnecessary procedural details such as 'The values of the latter were recorded in field books or digital devices.' Figures 6–8 showing sampling steps could be moved to Supplementary Material. Simplify over-detailed methodological descriptions and remove non-scientific instructions (e.g., 'practice a lot before commencing the sampling process,' 'check under daylight for bubbles'). Provide details relevant to the analytical precision, such as GC column type, detection limits, and isotopic accuracy.

4. Results

The Results section is rich but should focus solely on presenting data without interpretation. Interpretations belong in the Discussion. Values should be expressed as ranges with appropriate units, and isotopic notation must follow standard conventions ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{H}_2$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

The link between data and interpretation should be strengthened. Rather than listing numerous values, summarize and highlight key geochemical and isotopic trends (e.g., $\delta\text{D}-\delta^{18}\text{O}$ correlations, spatial variations in $\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2/\text{He}$) and discuss their geological implications.

Remove irrelevant details such as water potability discussions. Ensure tables contain measurement units. Clarify the purpose of blind samples—specify whether they served as analytical blanks or matrix controls—and verify the consistency of repeated samples (e.g., 'Katakali-2' and 'Kivotos-2').

5. Discussion

The Discussion lacks structure and clarity. It should be reorganized into subsections addressing specific scientific questions such as gas sources, migration pathways, trapping mechanisms, and implications. The discussion should be hypothesis-driven, directly linking interpretations to results. Currently, some parts of the Discussion are embedded in the Results section. These should be consolidated. Address the noted inconsistency: the manuscript claims that 'low silica enhances H_2 generation' but also that 'low silica can be indicated by magnetite.' In ultramafic contexts, magnetite is an indicator of serpentinization and thus hydrogen generation. Clarify this contradiction.

6. Minor, Technical, and Specific Comments

6.1 General Technical Corrections

- Ensure isotopic notation ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is consistently formatted using correct Greek symbols and superscripts (use 'O' not zero).
- Verify typographic consistency for isotopic symbols ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, δD , $\delta^{18}\text{O}$).
- Include measurement units consistently across all tables, particularly for δ -values and gas concentrations.
- Correct typographical errors such as '1..22' in Table 5 (double dot under dissolved O_2).
- Condense figures and tables to highlight only essential data; move over-descriptive figures to Supplementary Material.
- Clarify the expression 'public indications' (Page 10).
- Use consistent terminology: distinguish between 'potential gas-bearing formations' and 'storage reservoirs.'
- Replace outdated or irrelevant references with more recent sources.
- Rephrase ambiguous or awkward sentences for clarity, e.g., 'Hydrogen is highly reactive... preservation throughout migration is a risk' → 'Hydrogen is highly reactive and susceptible to redox conditions, making long-term preservation during migration challenging.'

- Rephrase 'This is also making sure...' → 'This is also to make sure...'
- Replace 'deploying natural hydrogen in the EU' with 'establishing a natural hydrogen economy in the EU.'
- Figures 6–8 show overly detailed sampling equipment. Consider moving these to Supplementary Material to streamline the main text.
- Clarify whether 'Katakali-2' and 'Kivotos-2' samples are duplicates or replicate analyses.
- Explain the rationale for using 'blind samples'—was bottled water used as an analytical blank or matrix control?

6.2 Page-Specific Remarks

Page 4, paragraph 5: Rephrase 'Natural hydrogen mechanisms...' as 'The understanding of natural hydrogen generation mechanisms is still under development.'

Page 4, paragraph 6: Adjust preservation and EU hydrogen economy phrasing as above.

Page 5, paragraph 6: Clarify the contradiction regarding silica content and H₂ generation mechanisms.

Page 10, paragraph 4: Differentiate between CO₂ storage and natural H₂ leakage—surface leaks may indicate deeper accumulations.

Page 10, paragraph 4: Clarify what is meant by 'public indications.'

Page 22, paragraph 2: Discuss the robustness of measurements given the small He/H₂ concentrations and analytical uncertainty.

Tables 2–5: Ensure δD–H₂O uses the letter O (not zero).

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the study provides valuable geochemical and isotopic data from a poorly documented region. However, its scientific impact would increase significantly if the manuscript were restructured around its core research questions, with redundant methodological details condensed. A stronger integration of geological, hydrogeochemical, and isotopic evidence would result in a clearer conceptual model of gas generation and migration in West Macedonia.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

No

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

I cannot comment. A qualified statistician is required.

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Geochimie et production de l'hydrogène naturel, migration et exploration.

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to state that we do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 05 Dec 2025

Pavlos Tyrologou

Response to report 1 Review of Tyrologou et al., Manuscript

General Assessment

The manuscript presents an integrated study on gaseous systems (H₂, He, CH₄, and CO₂) in Western Macedonia, combining structural geology, sedimentology, and geochemistry. This multidisciplinary approach is a major strength of the paper, as it provides valuable insights into the mechanisms controlling gas generation, migration, and trapping. The authors provide an extensive new geochemical dataset (gas chromatography, inductively coupled plasma, and isotope analyses) from both water and gas samples collected at multiple hydrothermal sources, which constitutes a significant contribution to the understanding of natural hydrogen systems.

Response: We thank the reviewers for their comments and feedback on the scientific concept of the manuscript. The authors truly appreciate the devoted volunteer time of the reviewer to support the rigorous process of scientific correction.

However, despite the richness of the data, the manuscript lacks clarity and focus. The research question and logical thread of the paper are often difficult to follow due to structural issues, redundancies, and digressions into socio-economic and political topics that are not directly relevant to a scientific article. The paper would benefit from a thorough reorganization following a classical structure (Introduction, Geological Context, Methods, Results, Discussion, and Conclusion). The clarity, conciseness, and scientific rigor of each section should be enhanced to help the reader clearly understand the problem, the methodology, and the conclusions.

Response: We thank the reviewers for their comments. The manuscript has now restructured along the suggested structure – Introduction, Geological Context, Methods, Results, Discussion and Conclusion.

Major Comments

1. Introduction

The Introduction is overly long and fragmented, which prevents a clear understanding of the main research question. It should be condensed into a coherent scientific narrative that succinctly states the problem, its significance, and the context of natural hydrogen. Political and environmental aspects should be summarized in two or three lines at most.

The manuscript would benefit from a clearer definition of its scientific novelty. While it compiles valuable field and isotopic data, the research question remains vague. The authors should explicitly state their hypothesis and objectives at the end of the Introduction to help readers understand the study's purpose.

Some statements are unclear or inaccurate; for example, 'Natural hydrogen mechanisms are still under development' should be rephrased as 'The understanding of natural hydrogen generation mechanisms is still under investigation.' The section 'Current State of the Art' lacks a detailed discussion of hydrogen production mechanisms and diverges into unrelated topics. It should focus on generation processes relevant to the study area and cite up-to-date references.

Response: Many thanks for your comments. The introductions has now been simplified and significantly shortened about political and environmental aspects to three lines . The introduction and current state of the art of natural hydrogen have merged into one. 'Natural hydrogen mechanisms are still under development' was rephrased as 'The understanding of natural hydrogen generation mechanisms is still under investigation.' A hypothesis and objectives have been explicitly stated together with the objectives. On the interest of saving space and keeping introduction short as requested by the reviewers, only the mechanisms of natural hydrogen are provided with the relevant references to the reader's interest. Providing more detail on the natural mechanisms for hydrogen will render the manuscript onto the review domain. The references provided have been updated and include additional newest ones where it makes sense, however the original ones kept as are still exceptionally valid.

2. Geological Context

The geological description is detailed and thorough, but overly extensive. Many details are not directly relevant to the research question and tend to obscure the main message. The section should focus on key aspects such as source rocks, basin thickness, structural controls (faults) on gas migration, and potential reservoir rocks. The authors should merge 'Previous research related to West Macedonia and neighbouring areas' with 'Geological setting' to avoid repetition. Maintain a logical flow—start with regional geology, then focus on specific study zones relevant to the presented data.

Response: We thank the reviewers for their comments. The sections now have been merged, and repetitions have been identified and deleted accordingly. The sections are now restructured to reflect the flow from supra regional to regional to local geology based on the reviewer's recommendations. **Clarify whether the study concerns West Macedonia or Greece, as this point remains ambiguous.** **Response:** We thank the reviewers for their comments. A specific phrase has been added in the hypothesis section in the introduction clarifying that West Macedonia is the focus of the study.

Figures 1–5 include excessive descriptive geological information. Simplifying these or adding a conceptual schematic linking tectonic setting, source rocks (ophiolites, lignites, carbonates), and migration pathways would greatly improve readability.

Response: Many thanks for your comment. Figure 1 and 3 have been deleted; a conceptual schematic is provided in figure 9 with the remaining figures **3. Materials and Methods** **The methodology is comprehensive but overly detailed. Only essential information should be provided—sample types, volumes, sampling conditions, and analytical tools. Avoid unnecessary procedural details such as 'The values of the latter were recorded in field books or digital devices.'** **Response:** Many thanks for your comment. The section has been cleaned of overly detailed procedural details, while ensuring that methods are described in sufficient detail for others to repeat the research in accordance with the Open Research Europe requirements. **Figures 6–8 showing sampling steps could be moved to**

Supplementary Material.

Simplify over-detailed methodological descriptions and remove non-scientific instructions (e.g., 'practice a lot before commencing the sampling process,' 'check under daylight for bubbles'). Provide details relevant to the analytical precision, such as GC column type, detection limits, and isotopic accuracy.

Response: Many thanks for your comments. The section has been cleaned of over-detailed procedural details, including non-scientific instructions. GC column type and detection limits for the gas analysis were added. We have kept Figures 6-8 to provide a reference for future readers who want to reproduce the methodology. We have provided and clarified the type of GC column, gas analysis detection limits and description of the isotopic precision (reproducibility) and accuracy (tracability) for all stable isotope measurements quantifying precision via one standard deviation values and ensuring accuracy through normalisation against international standards of SMOW, VSMOW2 and SLAP2 V-PDB. The analysis for He isotopes is also quantified, with its total analytical error, encompassing both precision and accuracy, stated as generally less than 1%. We understand isotopic accuracy on the basis of which international standard was used and which Certified Reference Materials (CRMs) were used for calibration with a statement on the final quantified uncertainty (\pm value) on the reported δ values. Regarding gas detection limits for H₂ we have modified the text in various places accordingly.

4. Results

The Results section is rich but should focus solely on presenting data without interpretation. Interpretations belong in the Discussion. Values should be expressed as ranges with appropriate units, and isotopic notation must follow standard conventions ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{H}_2$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Response: We thank the reviewers for their comments. We agree that, according to conventional scientific structure, interpretations should be presented primarily in the Discussion. However, given the complexity of the geochemical and isotopic datasets, we retained minimal and factual commentary within the results section to help guide the reader and enhance clarity. This includes brief contextualisation but avoids extensive interpretation or mechanism discussion. Nevertheless, we have reviewed the section again and relocated more detailed interpretations to the Discussion, in line with the reviewer's suggestion, while preserving clarity and narrative flow. Isotopic notations follow standard conventions ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{CH}_4}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2}$, $\delta\text{D}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) including Figure 9.

The link between data and interpretation should be strengthened. Rather than listing numerous values, summarize and highlight key geochemical and isotopic trends (e.g., $\delta\text{D}-\delta^{18}\text{O}$ correlations, spatial variations in $\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2/\text{He}$) and discuss their geological implications.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comments. A methane genetic diagram has been added to visualise results for Katakali and Kivotos.

Remove irrelevant details such as water potability discussions. Ensure tables contain measurement units. Clarify the purpose of blind samples—specify whether they served as analytical blanks or matrix controls—and verify the consistency of repeated samples (e.g., 'Katakali-2' and 'Kivotos-2').

Response: Many thanks for your comments. Certain details have been omitted to facilitate further the flow of the text. Text has been added to clarify the purpose of blind samples. Tables have been improved and contain measurement units. We clarify that 'Katakali-2' and 'Kivotos-2' are not analytical duplicates but independent field duplicates, i.e., separately collected samples from the same spring location. These were analysed in parallel to assess site-level variability. $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ values showed good agreement for Katakali (-69.5‰ vs -69.8‰), but $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$ differed by $\sim 21\text{‰}$. Kivotos showed greater variability (6.0‰ in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{CH}_4}$ and 15.0‰ in $\delta^2\text{H}_{\text{CH}_4}$), likely reflecting local heterogeneity rather than analytical error. A clarifying paragraph has been added before Table 8.

5. Discussion

The Discussion lacks structure and clarity. It should be reorganized into subsections addressing specific scientific questions such as gas sources, migration pathways, trapping mechanisms, and implications. The discussion should be hypothesis-driven, directly linking interpretations to results.

Response: We duly noted the reviewer's comments. These made us aware of the confusion, and we have now restructured the discussion section based on the scientific hypothesis, combined with the structure pointed out by the reviewer.

Currently, some parts of the Discussion are embedded in the Results section. These should be consolidated.

Response: Many thanks for your comment. Please see our answer above. The results section has been reorganised. Some minor interpretative text remains to facilitate the argument development as well as to help guide the reader and enhance clarity.

Address the noted inconsistency: the manuscript claims that 'low silica enhances H₂ generation' but also that 'low silica can be indicated by magnetite.' In ultramafic contexts, magnetite is an indicator of serpentinization and thus hydrogen generation. Clarify this contradiction.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comments and support in the rigorous scientific peer-review correction process. We acknowledge that the sentence structure is confusing and have improved it for clarity and corrected it accordingly to reflect the proper H₂ generation conditions. The section has also been enhanced with the addition of scientific references.

6. Minor, Technical, and Specific Comments

6.1 General Technical Corrections

- **Ensure isotopic notation ($\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CH}_4$, $\delta\text{D}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is consistently formatted using correct Greek symbols and superscripts (use 'O' not zero).** Response: Amended where needed

- **Verify typographic consistency for isotopic symbols ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, δD , $\delta^{18}\text{O}$).** Response: Amended where needed - **Include measurement units consistently across all tables, particularly for δ -values and gas concentrations.** Response: Amended where needed - **Correct typographical errors such as '1..22' in Table 5 (double dot under dissolved O₂).** Response: Corrected

Condense figures and tables to highlight only essential data; move over-descriptive figures to Supplementary Material.

Response: Many thanks for your comments. We believe that the current figures are essential for guiding the reader through the key geochemical and isotopic interpretations presented in the main text. They provide critical visual support for understanding the spatial and isotopic relationships discussed, and removing them may hinder the clarity and coherence of the narrative.

Clarify the expression 'public indications' (Page 10).

Response: Phrase was omitted as it provides the same meaning as the b) anecdotal data -

Use consistent terminology: distinguish between 'potential gas-bearing formations' and 'storage reservoirs.'

Response: Many thanks for your comments. We acknowledge the difference between the engineered or naturally suitable formations to inject and store gas such as CO₂ and the geological formations that naturally generate or contain gas. The ambiguity arose as the text described how the research evolved from the Pilot Strategy, a carbon capture and storage project. The ambiguity is resolved with the reorganisation of the text and the provision of a definition in the introductory section

- Replace outdated or irrelevant references with more recent sources.

Response: Thanks for your comments. We acknowledge the importance of incorporating recent literature and have reviewed the reference list accordingly. However, several of the cited long established sources remain foundational in the field and continue to be widely referenced by recent publications. Their inclusion ensures a robust conceptual framework and historical context, particularly where newer studies build directly upon or reaffirm these earlier works. Where appropriate, we have also cross-checked and added complementary recent references to demonstrate continuity and relevance with current scientific understanding. -

Rephrase ambiguous or awkward sentences for clarity, e.g., 'Hydrogen is highly reactive... preservation throughout migration is a risk' → 'Hydrogen is highly reactive and susceptible to redox conditions, making long-term preservation during migration challenging.'

Response: The authors are obliged by the constructive support of the reviewer and his thorough reading of the manuscript. We have rephrased as it was pointed out.

- Rephrase 'This is also making sure...' → 'This is also to make sure...'

Response: Corrected

- Replace 'deploying natural hydrogen in the EU' with 'establishing a natural hydrogen economy in the EU.'

Response: Many thanks for your suggestion, the phrase was deleted as part of the section shortening.

- Figures 6–8 show overly detailed sampling equipment. Consider moving these to Supplementary Material to streamline the main text.

Response: Many thanks for your comments and we appreciate the reviewer's suggestion to streamline the manuscript by relocating Figures 6–8 to the Supplementary Material. We respectfully believe that retaining these figures in the main body adds value by clearly illustrating the field methodology, which is essential for transparency and reproducibility, even if this sampling equipment is standardised. These visuals also enhance accessibility for readers who are less familiar with the equipment or protocols used in gas and water sampling.

- Clarify whether 'Katakali-2' and 'Kivotos-2' samples are duplicates or replicate analyses. Explain the rationale for using 'blind samples'—was bottled water used as an analytical blank or matrix control?

Response: Many thanks for your comments. The question remark has been clarified in the text and has also been answered in an aforementioned remark. We used two independent samples per site, taken minutes apart, to assess spatial or micro-scale variability within the same system. These are not laboratory duplicates or analytical replicates. An explanatory text has been added in the manuscript.

6.2 Page-Specific Remarks

Page 4, paragraph 5: Rephrase 'Natural hydrogen mechanisms...' as 'The understanding of natural hydrogen generation mechanisms is still under development.'

Response: Many thanks for your comments., text has been ammended

Page 4, paragraph 6: Adjust preservation and EU hydrogen economy phrasing as above.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comments , the phrase was deleted as part of the section shortening and restructuring.

Page 5, paragraph 6: Clarify the contradiction regarding silica content and H₂ generation mechanisms.

Response: We acknowledge that the sentence structure is confusing and have improved it for clarity and corrected it accordingly to reflect the proper H₂ generation conditions. The section has also been enhanced with the addition of scientific references.

Page 10, paragraph 4: Differentiate between CO₂ storage and natural H₂ leakage—surface leaks may indicate deeper accumulations.

Response: We thank the reviewer for their comment, which has strengthened the manuscript's scientific credibility. We have differentiated between CO₂ storage and hydrogen mobility based on their solubility properties. Text has been added in the corresponding paragraph for further clarification.

Page 10, paragraph 4: Clarify what is meant by 'public indications.'

Response: Phrase was omitted as it provides the same meaning as the b) anecdotal data

Page 22, paragraph 2: Discuss the robustness of measurements given the small He/H₂ concentrations and analytical uncertainty.

Response: We thank the reviewer for this important observation. Hydrogen and helium

were analysed by gas chromatography (Perkin Elmer Clarus 500 equipped with a double Carboxen 1000 packed column system and TCD-FID detectors), using Ar as the carrier gas. The TCD detection limit for H₂ and He is 1–10 µmol/mol (ppmv). The H₂ values reported are near the lower end of this range, and we acknowledge that such low concentrations require cautious interpretation. We still believe that the H₂ hold value since they were reproducibly detected at the same locations across multiple campaigns apart from us and show spatial coherence with ultramafic lithologies, major fault systems, and independent geochemical indicators such as alkaline pH, elevated Li–B, and reducing Fe–Mn conditions. We have added a new paragraph in the Discussion clarifying these points and acknowledging the limitations while demonstrating why the H₂ signals remain valid for interpretation. We appreciate the reviewer's comment, which has improved the transparency of our dataset interpretation.

Tables 2–5: Ensure δD–H₂O uses the letter O (not zero).

Response: Ammended

Overall Conclusion

Overall, the study provides valuable geochemical and isotopic data from a poorly documented region. However, its scientific impact would increase significantly if the manuscript were restructured around its core research questions, with redundant methodological details condensed. A stronger integration of geological, hydrogeochemical, and isotopic evidence would result in a clearer conceptual model of gas generation and migration in West Macedonia.

Response: We thank the reviewer for the constructive feedback and his commitment to the scientific review process. The manuscript was revised and restructured accordingly.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature? No

– **Response:** Thanks for your comments and we partially agree on the work that needs enhancement and needs to be clearer as it was described previously. The manuscript benefits from a very comprehensive literature review, we have included more references and we remain open to any additional literature that we may have missed by not being aware. Foundational sources are retained because they remain central in the current scientific literature, and more recent studies are built directly upon them. While every effort has been made to engage with the most relevant and up-to-date scientific literature, it is important to acknowledge a structural limitation inherent to the current scholarly landscape. A significant proportion of research outputs remains behind paywalls, as many authors publish in subscription-based journals. Access to these works is therefore restricted and not uniformly available across institutions or research teams, creating an unavoidable disparity in information accessibility. This manuscript reflects the fullest integration of all literature that was accessible through institutional subscriptions, open-access platforms, and publicly available databases at the time of writing. The authors strongly support the principles of open science, as unrestricted access to scientific publications and data is essential for ensuring equitable participation in research, fostering transparency, and accelerating scientific progress.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.